

WHO Guidelines for malaria

Systematic reviews, background papers and other unpublished evidence considered in the development of recommendations

Interventions in the final phase of elimination and prevention of re-establishment

Section

6.3.2 Reactive case detection and treatment to reduce transmission of malaria. In *WHO Guidelines for malaria*, 3 June 2022.

Title

Reactive case detection for reducing malaria transmission: A systematic review

Authors

Laura C. Steinhardt, Achuyt Bhattarai, Amanda Tiffany, Nicolas Laramée, Amy Large, and Kimberly A. Lindblade

Contact

gmpfeedback@who.int

This report was reviewed by the Guideline Development Group on Malaria Elimination, convened by the World Health Organization Global Malaria Programme to support the development of recommendations included in the *WHO Guidelines for malaria*. It is being made publicly available for transparency purposes and information, in accordance with the *WHO handbook for guideline development, 2nd edition (2014)*.

The designations employed and the presentation of the material in this publication do not imply the expression of any opinion whatsoever on the part of WHO concerning the legal status of any country, territory, city or area or of its authorities, or concerning the delimitation of its frontiers or boundaries. Dotted and dashed lines on maps represent approximate border lines for which there may not yet be full agreement.

The mention of specific companies or of certain manufacturers' products does not imply that they are endorsed or recommended by WHO in preference to others of a similar nature that are not mentioned. Errors and omissions excepted, the names of proprietary products are distinguished by initial capital letters.

All reasonable precautions have been taken by WHO to verify the information contained in this publication. However, the published material is being distributed without warranty of any kind, either expressed or implied. The responsibility for the interpretation and use of the material lies with the reader. In no event shall WHO be liable for damages arising from its use.

The named authors alone are responsible for the views expressed in this document.

Reactive case detection for reducing malaria transmission: A systematic review

By: Laura C. Steinhardt¹, Achuyt Bhattarai¹, Amanda Tiffany², Nicolas Laramee³, Amy Large³, and Kimberly A. Lindblade²

1. Malaria Branch, Division of Parasitic Diseases and Malaria, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, Atlanta, GA USA
2. Global Malaria Programme, World Health Organization, Geneva, Switzerland
3. Emory Rollins School of Public Health, Atlanta, GA

Table of Contents

Background	3
Objectives	3
Key question	3
Main objective	4
Secondary objectives	4
Methods.....	4
Types of study included	4
Types of participants/population and setting.....	5
Types of interventions	5
Types of outcome measures.....	6
Additional data abstracted	6
Search methods for identification of studies.....	7
Databases.....	7
Reference lists.....	8
Other	8
Data collection	8
Selection of studies	8
Data extraction and management	8
Risk of bias (quality) assessment	9
Strategy for data synthesis	9
Main outcome measures	9
Specification of effect modifiers for subgroup analysis of subgroups or subsets	10
Contextual factors.....	10

Modeling studies.....	11
Grading certainty of the evidence	11
Results.....	11
Description of studies	11
Results of the search.....	11
Included studies	12
Interventions.....	14
Outcomes.....	14
Contextual factors.....	15
Excluded studies	15
Risk of bias in included studies	15
Effects of interventions.....	20
Parasitemia prevalence.....	20
Confirmed malaria incidence	20
Adverse events.....	21
Parasitemia among those receiving RACD.....	21
Contextual factors.....	24
Acceptability.....	24
Feasibility and health systems consideration	24
Reactive case detection	24
Financial and economic considerations.....	25
Other numerical information on costs.....	25
Breakdown of cost components	25
Modeling studies.....	26
Discussion.....	26
References	37
Appendix 1: Definitions of outcomes and contextual factors	40
Appendix 2: Search terms and results	43
Appendix 3: Alternative forest plots for prevalence of parasitemia and incidence of confirmed malaria (with correct lower bound for 95% CI for Hsiang 2020(17)).....	45
Appendix 4: Detailed synthesis of contextual factors related to RACD.....	46

Background

Once malaria transmission declines to very low levels, case-based surveillance, namely reporting and investigating each passively-detected, parasitologically-confirmed malaria case (i.e. a symptomatic case presenting to a community health worker or a health facility), becomes feasible. Given the clustered nature of malaria cases at low transmission levels(1, 2), many countries pursuing malaria elimination have implemented strategies around parasitologically-confirmed malaria cases¹ in an effort to further reduce or interrupt transmission. Referred to as 'reactive' strategies, because they are initiated in response to confirmed cases, these actions may target both household members and neighbors of an index case, most commonly using reactive case detection (i.e. testing those around an index case for malaria and treating those positive with an antimalarial).

Testing people living with or near a confirmed malaria case for malaria and treating those positive with antimalarials, a strategy known as reactive case detection (RACD), has become increasingly common in low-transmission settings in the last decade. As of 2014, 13 of 14 countries in the Asia Pacific Malaria Elimination Network and several countries in Africa were implementing some form of RACD, either as a widespread programmatic intervention or as a pilot.(3) Operational approaches to RACD vary widely, with some RACD programs or studies testing only the index household members (Zanzibar national program),(4) while others target everyone living within a certain radius, including a 100- or 200-meter radius in Ethiopia(5)(6) or a 500-meter radius in Eswatini.(7) China has used an adapted approach with the size of the area to be targeted varying based on further classification of the local area of the index case (China national 1-3-7 program).(3) Previous studies have found that proximity to the index case(6, 7), a more sensitive diagnostic method,(3, 8, 9) timeliness of the response,(7) and recent travel(9) were positively related to the likelihood of finding secondary cases. Despite the popularity of RACD, evidence of its effectiveness is limited, and a 2016 systematic review concluded that it was labor-intensive and the benefits were not clear.(10)

Despite growing interest in RACD and more countries implementing them, there has not been a recent systematic evaluation of its effectiveness, although one older review (in 2016) on RACD has been published.(10)

Objectives

Key question

1. Should people residing with or near a confirmed malaria case be tested for malaria within one month of index case diagnosis and treated if positive to reduce human malaria transmission?

¹ There have also been studies that have conducted reactive strategies around cases identified through active surveillance. These studies will also be included in the review.

Main objective

1. To assess the benefits (on malaria transmission or burden) and harms (adverse effects) of testing and treating malaria-positive adults and children residing in the same household or near parasitologically-confirmed malaria cases

Secondary objectives

1. To assess contextual factors, including values and preferences, resource use, impact on equity, feasibility, and acceptability of RACD.
2. To summarize findings from mathematical modeling studies with respect to the impact of various operational factors on the modeled efficacy of RACD, including size or population of the intervention area, the antimalarial medications used, and other relevant factors.

Methods

Types of study included

Systematic review teams included studies that met eligibility criteria, regardless of language or publication status (published, unpublished, in press, and in progress). For the main objectives, types of eligible studies included the following, listed in order of descending robustness):

- Randomized designs
 - Cluster randomized controlled trials (cRCTs) with: (a) the unit of randomization being a cluster, and (b) at least two clusters per arm.
 - Randomized cross-over trials with: (a) the unit of randomization being a cluster, and (b) at least two clusters per arm.
 - Stepped wedge design where clusters are randomly allocated, with at least four clusters
 - Factorial design with at least two clusters per level
- Non-randomized designs
 - Quasi-experimental cluster-controlled trials with at least two clusters per arm
 - Controlled before-and-after designs with (a) a contemporaneous control group, and (b) at least two clusters per arm.
 - Interrupted time series (ITS) studies (with or without a contemporaneous control group) with: (a) a clearly defined point in time when the intervention occurred, and (b) at least three data points collected before the start of the intervention and (c) at least three data points after the intervention that cover the same malaria transmission season as the pre-intervention data points and (d) balanced co-interventions before and after the start of the reactive intervention.
 - Uncontrolled before-and-after studies (with a cluster design) or before-and-after studies with historical controls

Exclusion criteria included the following:

- Unit of randomization is at the individual level (for randomized trials)
- Unit of randomization is at the household level (for randomized trials)
- The intervention was administered to a subset of the population (i.e. based on age, occupation, etc.) in a defined geographic area
- Background malaria control interventions not evenly distributed/balanced across study arms
- Follow-up periods for intervention and control period not the same, or timing of baseline and endline surveys not at the same time in intervention and control
- Length of pre- and post-intervention periods for ITS studies are different (or cover different seasons)

For the secondary objectives (contextual factors and results from modeling studies), all study designs, including uncontrolled before-and-after studies, economic evaluations, qualitative studies, and other programmatic evaluations that include primary data, were considered.

Types of participants/population and setting

Adults and children of all ages living in areas with ongoing human malaria transmission or malariogenic potential were included.

Types of interventions

Intervention arm

RACD was defined as testing adults and children living with or near a confirmed malaria case for malaria and treating those positive with a full therapeutic course of antimalarials. There was no restriction on the type of antimalarial used as long as it was a therapeutic course. Treatment could also include an 8-aminoquinoline for radical treatment of hypnozoites of *Plasmodium vivax* and *P. ovale* index cases. Radical treatment was defined as a total dosage of 3.5–7 mg/kg of primaquine over 7 or 14 days or 8 weeks, depending on G6PD status, or as 300 mg of tafenoquine for those 16 years and older. Testing for malaria included parasitologic confirmation by a variety of methods, including rapid diagnostic tests (RDT), microscopy, or molecular methods such as loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP) and polymerase chain reaction (PCR). The intervention may or may not include screening for symptoms (e.g., fever) prior to testing, and this was considered as a potential effect modifier (see below). The intervention must have taken place in a setting that offers adequate access to case management and the ability to do case-based surveillance, i.e., conduct an investigation of each confirmed case and report cases at the individual, versus aggregate, level.

Comparator(s)/control

The comparator was no RACD (and could include another intervention, e.g., reactive drug administration (RDA)). Studies with multiple intervention arms were included.

Background interventions

Both intervention and control arms should have the ability to do case-based surveillance. Vector control may or may not be in place in the intervention and comparison arms but should be implemented to the same degree in both arms.

Types of outcome measures

Studies were included if they reported at least one main outcome for inclusion in the main analysis. Additionally, any studies reporting original data on contextual factors were included in the synthesis of contextual factors, and any study reporting results (in terms of the main outcomes) from mathematical modeling were included in the synthesis of modeling results.

Main outcomes (see Appendix 1 for a summary of outcomes and contextual factors)

Measured at community level

- 1) Incidence of malaria infection
- 2) Prevalence of malaria infection
- 3) Elimination (defined as 0 indigenous or local cases for a period during the peak transmission season)
- 4) Incidence of clinical malaria or number of indigenous malaria cases

Measured among those targeted by the intervention

- 5) Adverse events
- 6) Prevalence of infection

Additional data abstracted

Contextual factors

1. Values and preferences – The values and preferences of the individuals and populations affected by the recommendation with respect to the outcomes associated with the intervention;
2. Acceptability—Extent to which those benefiting from the intervention as well as other relevant stakeholder groups consider the intervention to be appropriate, based on anticipated or experienced cognitive and emotional responses to the intervention; includes willingness to participate in the intervention;
3. Health equity, equality and non-discrimination—Extent to which the intervention benefits all populations, does not discriminate against anyone on the basis of sex, age, ethnicity, culture, language, sexual orientation or gender identity, disability status, education, socioeconomic status, residence or any other characteristic. This could include whether the benefits and harms are equally distributed and whether the intervention is equally affordable and accessible to all;
4. Financial and economic considerations—Costs, resource intensiveness, overall economic impact, cost-effectiveness, cost-benefit;
5. Feasibility and health system considerations – legal barriers to implementation, interaction with existing health system, need for and use of the existing health workforce or other resources; programmatic considerations; timeliness (the ability to reach all targeted households/household members in a timely manner); adherence to drug completion among those given antimalarials; proportion of targeted population that is missed

Operational parameters

Insights from mathematical modeling on how variation in operational parameters alter the effectiveness of reactive drug administration were summarized for at least the following parameters, if available:

- Size or population of intervention area (e.g., radius) around the index case
- Antimalarial drug used
- Limits of detection/sensitivity of diagnostic test

Potential effect modifiers

The potential effect modifiers specified in Table 1 will be collected, when available, for each included study.

Table 1. Effect modifiers for each review for sub-group analyses

Primary effect modifiers (pre-specified sub-group analysis)	Additional effect modifiers to be collected
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Level of transmission² • Vector control coverage • Malaria parasite species (Pf, Pv, Po or Pm) of the index cases • Antimalarial medication used, including gametocytocide or hypnozoiticide • Use of symptom screening before testing • Limits of detection and sensitivity of the test • Size or population of intervention area (e.g., radius) around the confirmed case 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Whether all cases were included or only cases classified as local • Coverage of the intervention • Availability of G6PD screening (for Pv areas) • Rural vs. urban area

Search methods for identification of studies

We included all relevant studies regardless of date, language or publication status (published, unpublished, in press, ongoing). Evidence was only included if publicly available (currently or by the time of publication of this review) or if provisions could be made to post information on a public website. In addition to studies evaluating the efficacy or effectiveness of RACD, we screened all papers from the search for studies with information on relevant contextual factors or on potential effect modifiers.

Databases

Studies were identified through comprehensive electronic database searches using study-specific search terms (Appendix 2) and the following databases: Cochrane Infectious Diseases Group Specialized Register; Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL), published in The Cochrane Library;

² Across all questions, the level of transmission will be categorized according to the following schema found in the *Framework for malaria elimination*: High: incidence of about 450/1000 or Pf prevalence of >=35%; Moderate: incidence of 250-450 per 1000 and Pf/Pv prevalence of 10-35%; Low: incidence of 100-250 per 1000 and Pf/Pv prevalence of 1-10%; Very low: incidence of <100 per 1000 and Pf/Pv prevalence <1%.

MEDLINE (PubMed); EMBASE (OVID); and LILACS. We also searched Global Health; ProQuest Natural Science Collection; ZETOC; Tropical Diseases Bulletin; The Archives of the World Health Organization; US National Institute of Health Ongoing Trials Register (www.ClinicalTrials.gov/); ISRCTN registry (www.isrctn.com/); The WHO's International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (WHO ICTRP) (www.who.int.ictrp).

Reference lists

Forward and backward citation tracking was done for the reference lists of all studies and articles identified by the above methods and screened at the full text screening stage.

Other

The following conference proceedings were reviewed for relevant abstracts: Seventh Multilateral Initiative on Malaria Pan-African Malaria Conference (Dakar, Senegal; April 2018. Additionally, The Malaria Elimination Scientific Alliance assisted with conducting a 'Deep Dive' (<https://mesamalaria.org/mesa-track/deep-dives>) on RACD to identify planned and ongoing studies.

Data collection

Selection of studies

Two reviewers independently screened titles and abstracts identified from literature and other searches; any potentially relevant articles identified by at least one reviewer were evaluated by the same two reviewers for full-text eligibility based on pre-determined inclusion criteria. At the full-text screening stage, two independent reviewers used a checklist to assess eligibility for inclusion, with discrepancies resolved by a third reviewer.

Data extraction and management

Two reviewers independently extracted information (at the full-text article stage) from studies on a pre-piloted electronic data extraction form. Prior to beginning full text data abstraction, a calibration exercise was conducted using the data abstraction form to ensure good concordance among reviewers. Any discrepancies were resolved by discussion to reach consensus or by consultation with a third reviewer. We contacted the original study author(s) when needed to retrieve any missing data or for clarifications.

The following information was extracted:

- **Setting:** Country, transmission intensity and seasonality, antimalarial drug resistance context, parasite species of interest
- **Participants:** Population characteristics, demographics
- **Study design:** Type; method of randomization (if applicable) and participant selection; adjustment for clustering (for cluster-RCTs); sample size; method of blinding of participants and personnel with respect to each outcome of interest.
- **Intervention/comparison:** Diagnostic test(s) used; antimalarial(s) used; intended radius or number of households around index case; coverage (of intended households/household

members), timing (average time to intervention start after a confirmed index case); duration of intervention. Also, baseline coverage of malaria co-interventions in both intervention and control arms (if two-plus arms).

- **Outcomes:** Definition of outcome(s); diagnostic method or surveillance method for outcome measurement; population in which outcome was measured; number of events; number of participants or unit time; time point at which outcome was assessed in relation to start of intervention, statistical power; unit of analysis; incomplete outcomes or missing data; and results.
- **Contextual factors:** information on contextual factors (as defined under “Additional data abstracted”) was extracted from studies and summarized, but these data were not included in meta-analyses.

For dichotomous outcomes (e.g., prevalence), we extracted the number of prevalent cases (e.g., malaria infections) and number of participants (e.g., in a cross-sectional survey) in each study arm. For rate data (incidence), we extracted the number of events, the total person time at risk or population at risk in each study arm, and a measure of variance (standard error). For count data (number of indigenous malaria cases), we collected the number of events and the person-time or population over which they were reported.

For cluster RCTs we recorded the number of clusters randomized; number of clusters analyzed; measures of effect (such as risk ratio, odds ratio, or rate ratios) with confidence intervals (CI) or standard deviations; number of participants (e.g., population in which the outcome was measured); and the intracluster correlation coefficient (ICC) value, if available. We abstracted the adjusted effect estimates, both adjusted for clustering (if appropriate) and adjusted for other relevant covariates, as reported by study authors and using models that were pre-specified in study protocols.

For non-randomized studies, we extracted adjusted measures of intervention effects that attempted to control for confounding, including risk ratios and rate ratios.

Risk of bias (quality) assessment

Two members of the review team independently assessed the risk of bias for each included study using a tool designed to assess such risk on relevant domains as low risk, some concerns, or high risk and used summary graphs to display results. As the risk of bias in the effect of an intervention may be different for different outcomes, a ‘Risk of bias’ assessment for each outcome was made.

For each included RCT, the revised Cochrane ‘Risk of bias’ (ROB 2) tool(11) was used, along with other considerations in Chapter 8 of the Cochrane Handbook ‘Assessing risk of bias in a randomized trial’(12). Included RCTs were rated as low risk of bias, some concerns, or high risk of bias. We assessed non-randomized studies for risk of bias on standard criteria using slightly modified criteria from Table 2 in a recent publication on GRADE and risk of bias in non-randomized studies.(13)

Strategy for data synthesis

Main outcome measures

Measures of treatment effect

For study designs with a control group, the effect of the intervention was compared using risk ratios for dichotomous outcomes and rate ratios for rate, or counts, for example using Poisson regression or negative binomial analysis. For cluster-randomized trials, adjusted effect measures, both adjusted for clustering for other relevant covariates, as reported by study authors, constituted the primary measure of treatment effect. Since the randomized trials we included reported on the effect of RDA compared to RACD, we took the inverse of the effect size and confidence intervals reported and included that as the effect of RACD compared to RDA. When possible, we performed sensitivity analyses using unadjusted (for other covariates) effect measures to investigate the robustness of our analyses.

Dealing with missing data

We attempted to contact study authors to obtain any missing data. No data imputation was applied.

Assessment of heterogeneity

For outcomes with more than one study contributing data, we assessed heterogeneity of main effects by examining forest plots for overlapping CIs. Statistical heterogeneity was examined using the I^2 statistic and classified according to the criteria below:

- Moderate: I^2 between 30% and 60%
- Substantial: I^2 values between 50% and 90%
- Considerable: I^2 values between 75% and 100%

If there was either considerable heterogeneity (I^2 statistic value between 75% to 100%) or inconsistency in the direction of the effect, or both, then we did not perform a meta-analysis. Clinical and methodologic explanations for heterogeneity were considered when I^2 indicates substantial heterogeneity (i.e., $I^2 > 50\%$).

Data synthesis

For outcomes with more than one study contributing data, we used fixed effects meta-analysis to combine data if heterogeneity was absent, when there were only two studies, or when there were data from multiple small but biased studies and one well-conducted study. Otherwise, we combined data using a random effects meta-analysis and reported a pooled treatment effect. Studies using uncontrolled before/after study designs were not included in meta-analyses.

Specification of effect modifiers for subgroup analysis of subgroups or subsets

We attempted to stratify analyses of outcomes by potential effect modifiers (Table 1, above) if there were enough studies in each group.

Contextual factors

Information on contextual factors were grouped by contextual factor (from all study types) and presented in narrative summaries.

Modeling studies

Modeling studies were summarized in terms of their key findings with respect to likelihood of achieving outcomes and the effects of various model parameters. We assessed whether the model results supported or contradicted the findings from empirical studies.

Grading certainty of the evidence

Randomized trials (e.g. cluster RCTs, randomized cross-over trials, stepped wedge cluster randomized trials) started off with higher certainty than non-randomized studies (e.g. controlled before-and-after studies, ITS).

The certainty of evidence was evaluated using the GRADE approach(14) and each outcome was rated separately for evidence contributed by the randomized and non-randomized studies) as described by Balshem et. al.(15), using the GRADEPro software:

- High: we are very confident that the true effect lies close to that of the estimate of the effect.
- Moderate: we are moderately confident in the effect estimate. The true effect is likely to be close to the estimate of the effect.
- Low: our confidence in the effect estimate is limited. The true effect may be substantially different from the estimate of the effect.
- Very low: we have very little confidence in the effect estimate. The true effect is likely to be substantially different from the estimate of effect.

Randomized trials began as high-quality evidence but could be downgraded for valid reasons within the following five categories: risk of bias, imprecision, inconsistency, indirectness, and publication bias. Non-randomized studies began as low-certainty evidence but the certainty could be upgraded if there was a large effect, a dose response effect, and if all plausible residual confounding would reduce a demonstrated effect or would suggest a spurious effect if no effect was observed.(15)

Results

Description of studies

The included studies are described in more detail in Table 4; the excluded studies are listed along with their reason for exclusion in [Table 3](#).

Results of the search

A total of 1,323 unique records were identified from the database searches, after one duplicate was excluded, and 10 additional articles were identified from later full text screening. A total of 1,333 records were screened and 157 included for full text review. Of these, 116 were excluded for the reasons listed in **Figure 1** below. A total of 7 studies, including 3 randomized trials, 2 non-randomized studies, and 2 modeling studies, were included for outcome data; XX additional studies were included for contextual factors.

Figure 1: PRISMA Diagram

Included studies

Three randomized studies of RACD and two non-randomized studies were included for outcome data. The three randomized studies were cluster-randomized controlled trials (cRCTs) conducted in Zambia, Namibia, and Eswatini and intended to evaluate the effectiveness of RDA ((Bridges 2021(16), Hsiang 2020(17), and Vilakati 2021(18)). Because these three trials had RACD in the comparison arm, we evaluated them for the effect of RACD (compared to RDA). Two non-randomized studies were included. One uncontrolled before-and-after study from Zambia (Searle 2020(19)) evaluated parasitemia in households receiving RACD at 30 and 90 days. A second non-randomized trial, a controlled before-and-after study from Amazonia, Brazil (Fontoura 2016(20)) collected parasitemia data in RACD households and control households (>5 km distance) on days 0, 30, 60, and 180. Additionally, two modeling studies (Geradin 2017(21) and Reiker 2019(22)) on the effectiveness of RACD were identified to supplement empirical evidence. Tables 2 and 3 include summaries of the included empirical studies; comprehensive details are provided in Table 5.

Table 2: Summary details of included studies (for outcome data)

Study	Country	Year(s) of study	Study design	API	Primary malaria species	Study arms	Comparison	Drug used for RACD	Drug used for RDA	Area around index case	Diagnostic(s) used to define cases during RACD
<i>Randomized</i>											
Bridges 2021(16)	Zambia	2016–18	cRCT	12.7 per 1,000 in 2015	Pf	2-arm trial comparing RDA with RACD	RDA	AL	DP	140-meter radius	RDT (HRP2)
Hsiang 2020(17)	Namibia	2017	cRCT	35.9 per 1,000 in 2016	Pf	4-arm trial with factorial design: RDA, reactive IRS (+RACD), RDA+reactive IRS, and RACD)	RDA	AL + low-dose PQ	AL	500-meter radius	RDT (HRP2/pLDH) (Pf/PAN)
Vilakati 2021(18)	Eswatini	2016–17	cRCT	6.3 per 1,000 in RDA arm in 2012-2015	Pf	2-arm trial comparing RDA with RACD	RDA*	AL	DP	500-meter radius*	RDT (HRP2)
<i>Non-randomized</i>											
Searle 2020(19)	Zambia	2016–18	Uncontrolled before-after	1.3% PfPR in 2013	Pf	RACD only	No RACD	AL	N/A	250-meter radius	RDT (HRP2)
Fontoura 2016(20)	Amazonia (Brazil)	2013	Controlled before-after	5 per 1,000 in 2012	Pv	RACD in index/neighbor households, no RACD in control households	No RACD	CQ + low-dose PQ	N/A	5 closest households, up to 3km	Thick smear microscopy

cRCT = cluster randomized-controlled trial; MDA=mass drug administration; IRS=indoor residual spraying; Pf=Plasmodium falciparum; Pv=Plasmodium vivax; RDA= reactive drug administration; N/A=Not applicable; API = annual parasite incidence; DP=dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine; AL=artemether-lumefantrine; CQ=chloroquine; PQ=primaquine; PfPR=Plasmodium falciparum parasite rate; RDT = rapid diagnostic test; HRP2 = histidine-rich protein 2; pLDH=plasmodium lactate dehydrogenase

*RDA within a 200-meter radius

Table 3: Summary of outcomes in included studies

Study	Country	Outcomes				
		Incidence of parasitemia	Prevalence of parasitemia	Elimination/inter-ruption of malaria	Incidence of confirmed malaria	Adverse events
<i>Randomized</i>						
Bridges 2021(16)	Zambia		X		X	X
Hsiang 2020(17)	Namibia		X		X	X
Vilakati 2021(18)	Eswatini				X	X
<i>Non-randomized</i>						
Searle 2020(19)	Zambia					X
Fontoura 2016(20)	Amazonia (Brazil)					X

Interventions

Three cluster-randomized controlled trials (cRCTs) conducted in Zambia, Namibia, and Eswatini compared RACD, which was standard of care, or the standard intended to be implemented by the Ministry of Health, even if not carried out in practice, to RDA (Bridges 2021(16), Hsiang 2020(17), and Vilakati 2021(18)). The study in Namibia (Hsiang 2020(23)) used a factorial design with four arms: RDA, reactive IRS (plus RACD), RDA+reactive IRS, and RACD (considered the comparison); for the Namibia study we compared both RACD arms (with and without reactive IRS) to the RDA arm (with and without IRS). Among the five included studies, area around the index case for RACD ranged from a 140-meter radius (Bridges 2021(16)) to a 500-meter radius (Hsiang 2020(17)). The three randomized studies all used RDTs to detect secondary cases during RACD and all used artemether-lumefantrine (plus low-dose primaquine for transmission reduction in Namibia (Hsiang 2020(17)) for treatment.

One of the non-randomized studies in Zambia (Searle 2020(19)) used a 250-meter radius around the index case to test index case household members and neighboring household members with an RDT and treat with artemether-lumefantrine if positive. This study then followed up tested individuals and re-tested them (by RDT and PCR) again at 30 and 90 days. The second non-randomized study in the Amazonia region of Brazil (Fontoura 2016(20)) used microscopy to test the index case household members and those in the five nearest households (up to a 3-kilometer radius), and treat if positive with chloroquine and low-dose primaquine. The study team also tested members of five randomly selected control households (>5 kilometer's distance) from the same locality. All tested intervention and control participants were retested (by microscopy and by PCR) on days 30, 60, and 180.

Outcomes

Two studies (Bridges 2021(16), Hsiang 2020(17)) measured parasitemia prevalence (through a cross-sectional survey) after RACD. These two studies plus the third cluster-randomized trial (Vilakati 2021(18)) used routine data to assess the effect of RACD on confirmed malaria incidence. The three

randomized trials also included adverse outcomes, but the focus was primarily on the RDA arm. Prevalence of parasitemia among those receiving RACD was reported in the two non-randomized studies (Searle 2020(19) and Fontoura 2016(20)). No included studies assessed the impact of RACD on incidence of parasitemia or elimination/interruption of local transmission.

Contextual factors

No publications were identified that reported on values and preferences or equity of RACD. Four publications included information on RACD acceptability, nine publications reported on costs of RACD, and 17 reported on various aspects of feasibility of RACD.

Excluded studies

[To come if needed]

Risk of bias in included studies

Risk of bias is summarized separately for randomized and non-randomized studies below.

Randomized studies

Assessments for risk of bias for each study are summarized in **Figure 2** and **Figure 3** with additional details behind these judgements provided in the Table 4: Characteristics of included studies.

Randomization process

Two of the three studies (both except Vilakati 2021(18)) were rated as low risk of bias in terms of the randomization process. Both studies used acceptable randomization methods, such as computer-generated randomization (Hsiang 2020(17)) or picking clusters from a hat (Bridges 2021(16)). The Vilakati 2021(18) study was rated as 'Some concerns' given large imbalances in malaria incidence at baseline, resulting from inclusion only of clusters that had an incident case during the RDA period.

Recruitment of participants into clusters

Risk of bias for recruitment of participants into clusters was rated as low for two of the three cluster-randomized trials. For the Bridges 2021(16) trial in Zambia, the study authors speculated that there was a higher refusal rate in the RDA arm (compared to the RACD arm), and risk was therefore rated as 'Some concerns'.

Deviations from intended interventions

In two of the three studies, there were no notable deviations from the intended interventions except for the Eswatini study (Vilakati 2021(18)), where 20 RACD interventions were delivered in RDA arm (14 clusters) and 5 RDA interventions delivered in RACD arm through mix-ups; this study was rated as 'Some concerns' for risk of bias this domain.

Missing outcome data (for each outcome)

For parasitemia prevalence, the Namibia study (Hsiang 2020(17)) was rated as low risk of bias for missing outcome data. Data were collected through cross-sectional surveys, and there were no indications of differential missingness by study arm or high rates of missingness overall.

For the outcome of confirmed malaria incidence, all three studies contributing to this were rated as low risk. This outcome was reported through routine health system data in all relevant studies, and although not every study reported on the completeness or other quality aspects of routine data, it is unlikely that there were differential missingness or quality concerns by study arm, given the randomized nature of these studies.

For the outcome of adverse events, two of the three studies (Bridges 2021(16), and (Vilakati 2021(18)) were rated as high risk of bias for measurement of outcome. In these studies, there was no mention of adverse events being captured in the non-RDA arm. The Namibia trial (Hsiang 2020(23)) was rated as some concerns as one adverse event was reported from the RACD arm, although it is likely that the focus on adverse event reporting was much more intensive in the RDA arm.

Measurement of outcome (for each outcome)

For parasitemia prevalence, the Namibia trial (Hsiang 2020(23)) was rated as low risk of bias. Parasitemia prevalence was measured in a cross-sectional survey by PCR conducted at a later time point in the laboratory. It is highly unlikely that laboratory staff would deliberately change their interpretation of PCR results based on (unlikely) knowledge of a participant's study arm.

For confirmed malaria incidence, all three studies were rated as low risk, given that it is unlikely that clinicians at health centers would know which study arm the patient is from and use that knowledge to alter their diagnostic or treatment practices.

For the outcome of adverse events, all three studies were rated as high risk of bias. Studies typically had much more proactive approaches to detecting adverse events (such as follow-up visits to households receiving RDA) in the RDA arm compared to the RACD or comparison arm.

Selection of reported result (for each outcome)

For all three outcomes, all studies contributing to the outcome were rated as low risk of bias. All outcomes were pre-specified. In some cases the covariates for adjustment of the outcome effect were not pre-specified but all authors reported on the reasoning for inclusion of these covariates.

Figure 2: Risk of bias summary for randomized studies: review authors' judgements about each risk of bias item for each included study

	Randomization process	Recruitment of participants into clusters	Deviations from intended interventions	Missing outcome data: Parasitemia prevalence	Missing outcome data: Confirmed malaria incidence	Missing outcome data: Adverse events	Measurement of outcome: Parasitemia prevalence	Measurement of outcome: Confirmed malaria incidence	Measurement of outcome: Adverse events	Selection of reported result: Parasitemia prevalence	Selection of reported result: Confirmed malaria incidence	Selection of reported result: Adverse events
Bridges 2021	+	?	+		+	-		+	-		+	+
Hsiang 2020	+	+	+	+	+	?	+	+	-	+	+	+
Vilakati 2021	?	+	?		+	-		+	-		+	+

Note: 'Unclear risk of bias' should be interpreted as 'Some concerns'.

Figure 3: Risk of bias graph for randomized studies: review authors' judgements about each risk of bias item presented as percentages across all included studies

Note: 'Unclear risk of bias' should be interpreted as 'Some concerns'.

Non-randomized studies

The two non-randomized studies (Searle 2020(19) and Fontoura 2016(20)) were rated separately from the randomized studies on risk of bias domains. They were both rated as low risk of bias for appropriate eligibility criteria, given the clearly defined case definition for index case and geographic proximity criteria for RACD. Since the only outcome for these two studies was parasitemia prevalence among those receiving RACD, by definition all those included in this measurement had received RACD, thus we rated the domain for measurement of exposure as low risk of bias. Similarly, measurement of the outcome was done by PCR for both studies and it is highly unlikely that test interpretation would have been influenced by knowledge of the RACD intervention. Regarding control for confounding, the study in Brazil (Fontoura 2016(20)) was rated as low risk given the inclusion of control households; however, the non-randomized study in Zambia (Searle 2020(19)) was considered high risk on this domain given the lack of control group or adjustments for any seasonal or secular trends during the study period. Finally, the Brazil study (Fontoura 2016(20)) was rated as low risk in terms of complete follow up given the high participation rates in both intervention and control households during follow-up visits; the Zambia study (Searle 2020(19)) was rated as some concerns given decreasing follow-up over time, with less than 70% participation by the second household visit.

Figure 4: Risk of bias summary for non-randomized studies: review authors' judgements about each risk of bias item for included study

	Appropriate eligibility criteria	Measurement of exposure (i.e. intervention)	Measurement of outcome	Adequate control of confounding	Complete follow-up
Fontoura 2016	+	+	+	+	+
Searle 2020	+	+	+	-	?

Note: 'Unclear risk of bias' should be interpreted as 'Some concerns'.

Figure 4: Risk of bias graph for non-randomized studies: review authors' judgements about each risk of bias item presented as percentages across all included studies

Note: 'Unclear risk of bias' should be interpreted as 'Some concerns'.

Effects of interventions

Parasitemia prevalence

One study in Namibia (Hsiang 2020(23)) comparing RACD to RDA included parasitemia prevalence as an outcome. For the Namibia trial, we abstracted data from the analysis model that was pre-specified in the study protocol (adjustment for baseline imbalances only); Compared to RDA, and adjusted for other covariates, there was a non-significant higher odds of parasitemia in the RACD arm: odds ratio = 1.85 (95% CI: 0.96, 20.00). It is important to note that authors of the Namibia trial calculated the effect size using marginal effects post-estimation (to account for reactive IRS in half the clusters) after a regression model, thus the 95% confidence interval (CI) bounds are not balanced around the point estimate; as the Review Manager software can only accommodate balanced CIs, the 95% CI in Figure 5 contains the correct lower bound but is artificially narrow. A sensitivity analysis with the correct upper bound (but an artificially wide CI) is provided in Appendix 3.

Figure 5: Forest plot of comparison: RACD versus RDA on parasitemia prevalence

Footnotes

- (1) The 95% CI upper limit presented here is lower than in the published paper (odds ratio = 1.85, 95% CI: 0.96, **20.00**). Effect size from (non-linear) marginal effect post-estimation from generalized estimating equations (GEE) model using a logit function adjusted for reactive IRS, the interaction between reactive IRS and RDA, 2016 incidence of local cases, index case level and target population coverage for RDA or RACD, response time, and co-interventions by Namibia MoH. Unadjusted effect size (from post-estimation marginal effect of RDA from GEE model using a logit function adjusted for reactive IRS, the interaction between reactive IRS and RDA but no other covariates): 0.95 (95% CI: 0.48, 33.3).

Confirmed malaria incidence

Three randomized trials (Bridges 2021(16), Hsiang 2020(17), and Vilakati 2021(18)) assessed the effect of RACD compared to RDA, adjusted for other covariates, for confirmed malaria incidence. Two trials, one in Zambia (Bridges 2021(16)) and the second in Eswatini (Vilakati 2021(18)), found a small but non-significant increase in confirmed malaria incidence from RACD compared to RDA: rate ratios = 1.25 (95% CI: 0.78, 2.01) and 1.22 (95% CI: 0.58, 2.57), respectively. The third trial in Namibia (Hsiang 2020(23)) reported a slightly larger but still non-significant increase in confirmed malaria incidence in the RACD arm compared to the RDA arm: rate ratio = 1.41 (95% CI: 0.83, 4.55). (For the Namibia trial, we abstracted data from the analysis model that was pre-specified in the study protocol (adjustment for baseline imbalances only.) The authors of the Namibia trial calculated the effect size using marginal effects post-estimation (to account for reactive IRS in half the clusters) after a regression model, thus the 95% confidence interval (CI) bounds are not balanced around the point estimate; as the Review Manager software can only accommodate balanced CIs, the 95% CI in Figure 6 contains the correct

lower bound but is artificially narrow. A sensitivity analysis with the correct upper bound (but an artificially wide CI this this trial) is provided in Appendix 3. The pooled estimate across the three trials for confirmed malaria incidence comparing RACD to RDA showed a non-significant increase in confirmed malaria incidence: rate ratio = 1.30 (95% CI: 0.94, 1.79). The sensitivity analysis (Appendix 3) also showed a non-significant increase: rate ratio = 1.26 (95% CI: 0.86, 1.84).

Figure 6: Forest plot of comparison: RACD versus RDA on confirmed malaria incidence

Footnotes

- (1) Negative binomial analysis of monthly facility cases (random intercept for facility); adjusted for previous month's cases, NDVI, precipitation, altitude, night-time light, number RDTs done each month, and seasonality (fourier term). Unadjusted estimate: 0.93 (0.77, 2.00)
- (2) The 95% CI upper limit is lower here than in the published paper (1.41 (95% CI: 0.83, **4.55**); estimate from (non-linear) marginal effect post-estimation from a negative binomial model with offset for cluster-level person time; adjusted for reactive vector control, interaction between RDA and reactive vector control, 2016 incidence of local cases, index case level and target population coverage for RACD or RDA, response time, and co-interventions by Namibia Ministry of Health. Unadjusted marginal effects from post-estimation (from unadjusted negative binomial model with terms for RACD, reactive IRS, and the interaction between the two, with offset for cluster-level person time): 1.22 (0.73, 3.85).
- (3) Negative binomial regression model of local cases with offset for person-time and adjusted for baseline (2014-2015) incidence of local cases. Unadjusted estimate: 0.94 (95% CI: 0.51, 1.75).

Adverse events

Three randomized trials reported on adverse events (AEs); however, AEs were typically only actively solicited from the RDA arm and not from the RACD arm. In the Zambia trial comparing RACD using artemether-lumefantrine (AL) with RDA using dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine (DP) (Bridges 2021(16)), 123 (6.9%) mild AEs occurred in 1,775 people treated with DP (all resolved); no events were reported from the RACD arm. In the Namibia trial (Hsiang 2020(23)) of RACD with AL compared to RDA with AL, the authors reported that 1 participant of 96 (1.0%) treated in the RACD arm experienced an AE compared to 17 of 4,247 treated participants (0.4%) in the RDA arm; 11 AEs were considered unrelated, 6 possibly related, and 6 probably related. In the Eswati trial (Vilakati 2021(18)), no AEs were reported from participants who received AL in the RACD arm and 68 (3.8%) of 1,776 participants receiving RDA with DP were reported to experience AEs; 54 were rated as mild and 14 as moderate.

Parasitemia among those receiving RACD

Two non-randomized studies (Searle 2020(19) and Fontoura 2016(20)) assessed parasitemia after the intervention among those receiving RACD. In the non-randomized study in Brazil, households receiving RACD, along with control households (in the same locality but >5 kilometer's distance, were followed up

at 30, 60, and 180 days after RACD and tested by microscopy and PCR. In the Zambia non-randomized study (Searle 2020(19)), individuals in households (index case and neighboring) that received RACD were followed up and tested again by RDT and PCR at 30 and 90 days. Results from a difference-in-differences analysis of the Brazil study indicate a slight increase (by 0.8 percentage(%)-points, 3.8%-points, and 2.3%-points at 30, 60, and 180 days, respectively) in parasitemia over time in RACD households compared to control households. The Zambia study indicated a slight decrease (by 0.9%-points and 2.1%-points at 30 and 90 days after RACD, respectively) in parasitemia in RACD households, but no control households were included. RDT results from both studies (not shown) were similar.

Table 4: Parasite prevalence by PCR among those receiving RACD in non-randomized studies

Study	Intervention, n/N (%)					Control, n/N (%)					Difference from Day 0 or difference-in-differences, in percentage points*			
	Day 0	Day 30	Day 60	Day 90	Day 180	Day 0	Day 30	Day 60	Day 90	Day 180	Day 30	Day 60	Day 90	Day 180
Fontoura 2016	59/821 (7.2%)	63/788 (8.0%)	46/799 (0.3%)	NA	44/832 (5.3%)	35/631 (5.6%)	35/626 (5.6)	2/634 (0.3%)	NA	9/676 (1.3%)	0.8%	3.8%	NA	2.3%
Searle 2020	88/2,215 (3.7%)	44/1,556 (2.8%)	NA	22/1,333 (1.7%)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	-0.9%	NA	-2.1%	NA

* Estimates indicate the difference-in-differences for Fontoura 2016: $[(\%Pos-Intervention_{post} - \%Pos-Intervention_{Day0}) - (\%Pos-Control_{post} - \%Pos-Control_{Day0})]$ and differences from Day 0 $(\%Pos-Intervention_{post} - \%Pos-Intervention_{Day0})$ for Searle 2020.

Contextual factors

Acceptability

Sociocultural acceptability

Community and health care worker's acceptability data were abstracted from 4 studies from Cameroon(24), Namibia(25), Senegal(26), and Zambia(27). Community acceptance of RACD was high (refusal rate 2% or lower). In Namibia, some "hesitation/resistance" during pre-trial was reported but community engagement and sensitization appear to have helped participation. Similarly, in Senegal the high RACD participation has been attributed to advanced cascade sensitization, making follow-up appointments for absent members, and conducting return visits to the compound the same or next day. Lack of community confidence in community health care workers (CHWs) ability to address diseases other than malaria and community unwillingness to visit CHWs for malaria testing were reported from Zambia (27).

Health Care Worker Acceptability

There were no studies reporting data directly on health care workers' (HCWs) acceptance of RACD. Related information was abstracted from two studies. In Zambia(27), CHWs reported lack of motivation to conduct RACD, which was in part linked to CHWs feeling their community service went unrecognized. In Cameroon, CHWs thought conducting only a 1day visit per week to health facilities and only to households of index cases was more productive(24). The lack of stipend or financial support was the biggest problem noted by CHWs who were volunteers.(27)

Feasibility and health systems consideration

Index case detection and investigation

Index case notification from private health facilities was low and these cases are largely reported to be missed by RACD in Cambodia(28, 29) and Zanzibar(4). Within the public health sector, delayed presentation of malaria patients to health facilities, poor preparation of village clinics to participate in surveillance programmes, and the lack of adequate human resources and malaria RDTs have been reported as barriers and challenges to effective RACD(30). Complexity of case investigation procedures and lack of standard operating procedures have been identified as barriers to effective case investigation (30). Case classification (imported v. indigenous) difficulty has also been reported due to incomplete travel histories(30, 31).

During peak malaria transmission seasons in Zambia, the proportion of case investigations conducted were lower than other times mainly due CHWs being overwhelmed by patient volume as well as inadequate malaria rapid diagnostic test. To overcome these barriers, authors have suggested that the programme would benefit from additional CHWs or suspension of RACD.

Reactive case detection

Barriers to timely follow-up during RACD have been reported due to difficulty accessing mountainous terrains(32), flooded areas(27), and border areas with highly mobile populations(32). To overcome barriers posed by flooding during rainy season, study authors from Zambia recommend that CHWs, particularly who serve flood-prone areas, should be provided with rain gear and access to boats (27). Another barrier to effective RACD was the large numbers of households to screen, particularly in high density areas of the Asia Pacific regions(33). Imported cases pose a major challenge for RACD. District-level responses alone are unlikely to be ineffective in interrupting transmission when most malaria cases

are imported from outside the district (28). Communication and surveillance linkages with other operational

A key barrier in conducting effective RACD is malaria rapid diagnostic test (RDT) stockouts which prevented testing around index cases(23) as well as the low sensitivity of RDTs and the inability of *Plasmodium falciparum* specific RDTs to detect other species and low-density infections(30, 34, 35) To overcome these challenges, loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP) or other more sensitive diagnostics have been recommended(30, 35).

Lack of HCWs to conduct malaria activities and lack of surveillance officers at district level have been reported to result in inadequate supervision, case investigation and follow-up(36). Lack of motivation among HCWs to pursue case investigation and contact testing, particularly during weekends and public holidays has also been reported(28). Maintaining workforce motivation and providing consistent support, supervision and incentives have been recommended to overcome these challenges(27, 28).

Household coverage by RACD

The proportion of eligible households reached by RACD varies across different geographic locations (**Table 4**), with 49% of index case households investigated in Zanzibar to 100% in Jiangsu, China. Similarly, the proportion of households reached in a timely manner also varies across different locations, from about 20% in Zanzibar to 100% in China.

Adherence to antimalarials among those treated

Adherence to artemether-lumefantrine (AL) was reported from one study in Namibia which found nearly 100% adherence in 368 individuals who had their blister packs at follow-up pill counts. Among individuals without their blister packs (n=316), all but one reported full adherence to AL.

Financial and economic considerations

Cost per person screened

The cost per person screened during RACD was reported from 3 countries (Table 5). The average cost of screening varies across different regions, with US \$5.21 in Thailand to US \$27.6 in Indonesia, where the general cost of screening one individual during RACD was \$11, with an additional microscopy cost of \$0.62 per person and \$16 per person for LAMP(37). In Senegal, the cost per person screened by RACD was US \$14.3 (38).

Other numerical information on costs

Costing models developed(39) based on experience of implementing partners, operational documents and costing studies from Ethiopia, Senegal, and Zambia, show the average annual financial cost per capita (total population of 360,000 based on 1 region, 3 districts, 20 HFCA each, 6000 population per HFCA) were \$1.07 for the first year of RACD, and \$0.65 per year for the next 5 years (USD, 2014) and the per capita economic cost was \$1.27 in first year of RACD, and \$0.75 per year for the next 5 years (USD, 2014).

Breakdown of cost components

RACD costs totals show variation between study areas ranging from \$3,469 in Indonesia to \$10,486 in Thailand for total personnel and \$257 (Indonesia) to \$13,969 (Thailand) for commodities, services and other costs(36). These variations in personnel, commodities, services, and other costs specific to case investigation and RACD activities reported are likely due to differences in programme structure and level of integration of malaria related activities into the broader healthcare system(36).

In Zambia, the mean annual cost of RACD per health facility catchment area (HFCA) was \$1177 (median = \$923, IQR \$651–\$1417)(40). The variation in costs was driven by the number of CHWs and passive cases detected. CHW-related costs and data review meetings accounted for the largest share of costs. RDTs and drugs accounted for less than 10% of total costs.

Modeling studies

The first modeling study(41) used three scenarios from southern Zambia (low transmission, high household density, high transmission, low household density, and high transmission high household density using a dynamical model (EMOD v2.10) of malaria transmission. The simulations found that in low-transmission areas, improved case management and control of imported malaria alone was sufficient to interrupt transmission, with little additional benefit from RACD; in higher-transmission, low population density settings (malaria prevalence ranging from 5 – 50%), excellent case management (all cases were treated in the simulation) had to be in place before RACD had any effect, and it only had an appreciable effect if MDA was also added as an intervention. In higher-transmission, higher population-density settings, modeling indicated that elimination was less likely overall and the addition of RACD did not improve the chances of elimination.(41)

The second study used OpenMalaria, an individual-based stochastic model, to simulate RACD in a setting similar to Zambia and assessing the contribution of RACD to malaria elimination under a variety of parameters. The authors found that case management and EIR (i.e., transmission level) were the most important determinants of the probability of malaria elimination(22); they found that RACD had an inverse relationship with EIR and that RACD with the aim of transmission interruption is only appropriate where transmission is very low (defined by the authors as EIR of 1 -2 or parasite prevalence of <7% - 19%).

Discussion

[To come pending GDG discussion]

Table 5. Description of included studies

Randomized studies

Bridges 2021

<p>Methods</p>	<p>Location: Southern Province, Zambia</p> <p>Study dates: May 2016 – May 2018</p> <p>Baseline annual parasite incidence: ~3 per 1,000</p> <p>Study design: Cluster-randomized trial</p> <p>Unit of randomization: Health facility catchment area</p> <p>Total number of clusters (total): 16</p> <p>Clusters in RACD arm: 8</p> <p>Total population in RACD arm: ~56,000</p> <p>Total population in RDA arm: ~63,000</p> <p><i>Note that this study is a cluster-randomized trial focused on RDA, with RACD serving as the comparison arm. In our case, the focus is on RACD as the intervention arm, with RDA serving as the comparison arm.</i></p>
<p>Participants</p>	<p>Number of RACD ‘events’: 392</p> <p>Number of household members/neighbors tested: 3,953</p> <p>Number of household members/neighbors positive: N/A</p> <p>Number of household members/neighbors treated: 118</p> <p>Percent treated of total targeted: N/A</p>
<p>Interventions</p>	<p><u>Intervention:</u></p> <p>Drug(s) used for RDA: Artemether-lumefantrine</p> <p>Index case detection: Through passive surveillance at health facilities and CHWs</p> <p>Area targeted around index case: 140 meters</p> <p><u>Comparison:</u></p> <p>Type: Reactive drug administration with dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine and a 140-meter radius</p> <p><u>Co-interventions:</u> ITNs, IRS, good malaria case management</p>
<p>Outcomes</p>	<p><u>Prevalence of parasitemia:</u></p> <p>Measurement: Cross-sectional household survey</p>

	<p>Persons sampled: Children aged ≥ 1 month to < 15 years</p> <p>Diagnostic test used: PCR</p> <p>Time point(s): One time post-intervention (April–May 2018)</p> <p>Sample size: 3,125 (RACD), 3,151 (RDA)</p> <p><u>Incidence of clinical cases:</u></p> <p>Measurement: Weekly and monthly routine data on malaria cases (clinical and laboratory-confirmed) from community health workers and facilities accessed through DHIS2</p> <p>Time points: May 2016 – May 2018</p> <p><u>Adverse events:</u></p> <p>No adverse events reported from RACD arm (using AL). From RDA arm, where dihydroartemisinin-piperazine used in RDA arm, 123 reported only in RDA arm: headache (20%), abdominal pain (17%), dizziness (17%), or nausea (16%). All were mild and self-resolved.</p>
Notes	

Risk of bias

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Randomization process	Low risk	Clusters were picked from a hat.
Recruitment of participants into clusters	Some concerns	Authors speculated there was a higher refusal rate in RDA arm.
Deviations from intended interventions	Low risk	No evidence that incorrect interventions delivered.
Missing outcome data (clinical malaria incidence)	Low risk	Authors reported no missing routine data (per correspondence)
Measurement of outcome (adverse events)	High risk	Adverse events reported only in RDA arm
Measurement of outcome (clinical malaria incidence)	Low risk	Data collected at health facilities and by CHWs for clinical management.
Measurement of outcome (adverse events)	High risk	Unclear whether adverse events reported from non-RDA arm
Selection of reported result (clinical malaria incidence)	Low risk	Outcome was pre-specified.
Selection of reported result (adverse events)	Low risk	Standard adverse events reported.

Hsiang 2020

Methods	<p>Location: Zambezi region, northern Namibia</p> <p>Study dates: January–December 2017</p> <p>Baseline annual parasite incidence: 32.5 per 1,000 in 2016 (previously < 15 per 1,000 since 2010)</p>
---------	--

	<p>Study design: Cluster-randomized trial with factorial design: RDA, reactive vector control, both, and control</p> <p>Unit of randomization: Census enumeration area</p> <p>Total number of clusters (total): 56</p> <p>Clusters in RACD arm: 28 (14 also with reactive IRS)</p> <p>Total population in RACD arm: ~16,500 (total population in catchment areas = 33,418)</p> <p>Total population in control/comparison arm: ~16,500</p> <p><i>Note that this study is a cluster-randomized trial with a factorial design testing RDA, reactive IRS, and both interventions. The RACD arm was considered the 'control' but for this review, we compared the RACD arm to the RDA arm, considering the latter as the 'control'.</i></p>
Participants	<p>Number of RACD 'events': 178</p> <p>Number of household members/neighbors tested: 4,701</p> <p>Percent tested of total targeted: $4,701/5,296 = 88.7\%$</p> <p>Number of household members/neighbors positive: 114</p> <p>Number of household members/neighbors treated: 98</p>
Interventions	<p><u>Intervention:</u></p> <p>Drug(s) used for RACD: Artemether-lumefantrine plus low-dose (0.25 mg/kg) primaquine</p> <p>Index case detection: Through passive surveillance at 11 health facilities (total for the trial)</p> <p>Area targeted around index case: Households within a 500-meter radius, with a target up at least 25 individuals</p> <p><u>Comparison:</u></p> <p>Type: Reactive case detection with artemether-lumefantrine targeting households within a 500-meter radius</p> <p><u>Co-interventions:</u> Case management, annual IRS with DDT; R-IRS in half the clusters</p> <p><i>Note that half the RDA and half the reactive case detection clusters also had reactive indoor residual spraying (R-IRS).</i></p>
Outcomes	<p><u>Prevalence of parasitemia:</u></p> <p>Measurement: Cross-sectional household survey</p> <p>Persons sampled: All household members</p> <p>Diagnostic test used: PCR</p> <p>Time point(s): May – August 2017</p>

	<p>Sample size: 2,150 (RACD), 1,932 (RDA)</p> <p>Analysis: Authors used a log binomial regression with a log link to estimate prevalence ratios using generalized estimating equations to adjust for enumeration area-level clustering. Models included terms for RDA, for reactive IRS, and the interaction between the two. Adjusted model also included 2016 incidence of local cases, index case level and target population coverage for RAD or RDA, response times, and co-interventions by the Ministry of Health.</p> <p><u>Incidence of clinical cases:</u></p> <p>Measurement: Routine data on malaria cases diagnosed by microscopy and RDT at health facilities</p> <p>Time points: Jan 2017 – December 2017</p> <p>Analysis: Negative binomial regression using a generalized linear model to estimate incidence rate ratios using cluster-level case data and cluster person-time as an offset. Models included terms for RDA, for reactive IRS, and the interaction between the two. Adjusted model also included 2016 incidence of local cases, index case level and target population coverage for RAD or RDA, response times, and co-interventions by the Ministry of Health. Note that cases and person-time counted starting only 8 weeks after the first intervention administered in each cluster.</p> <p><u>Adverse events:</u></p> <p>It is unclear how AEs were detected in the RACD arm. In the RDA arm, AEs were detected by having participants call an on-call study nurse and by follow-up visits by a study nurse among a portion of those receiving artemether-lumefantrine. In total 23 AEs in 18 individuals were reported, including headache (n=5), dizziness (n=5), diarrhea (n=3), vomiting (n=2), abdominal pain (n=2), fever (n=2), and weakness, cough, decreased appetite and muscle pain (1 each); 19 (83%) AEs were mild (grade 1) and four (17%) were moderate (grade 2). 17 (74%) of 23 adverse events were actively detected at follow-up visits. Six AEs were classified as probably related to treatment, 6 as possibly related, and 11 as unrelated. Of the 18 participants reporting at least one AE, 17 were in the RDA group and 1 in the RACD group.</p>
--	--

Risk of bias

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Randomization process	Low risk	Computer-generated restricted randomization used but baseline imbalances (in annual parasite incidence) in 2016 between arms
Recruitment of participants into clusters	Low risk	Unlikely to have been differential recruitment by arm; participation rates similar across arms
Deviations from intended interventions	Low risk	No evidence of wrong intervention or deviations due to trial context

Missing outcome data (parasitemia prevalence)	Low risk	Equal numbers of children per arm sampled; no evidence of differential missingness
Missing outcome data (clinical malaria incidence)	Low risk	Based on routine data reported; no evidence of differential missingness
Missing outcome data (adverse events)	Some concerns	Unclear to what extent adverse events were captured in the RACD arm (although one adverse event reported from RACD arm).
Measurement of outcome (parasitemia prevalence)	Low risk	PCR done in the laboratory; unlikely that analysis affected by knowledge of study arm
Measurement of outcome (clinical malaria incidence)	Low risk	Routine diagnosis at health facilities; unlikely that diagnosis affected by knowledge of study arm
Measurement of outcome (adverse events)	High risk	Likely that adverse event reporting was much stronger in RDA arm compared to reactive case detection arm.
Selection of reported result (parasitemia prevalence)	Low risk	Pre-stated outcome
Selection of reported result (clinical malaria incidence)	Low risk	Pre-stated outcome
Selection of reported result (adverse events)	Low risk	Pre-stated outcome

Vilakati 2021

Methods	<p>Location: eastern malaria-endemic areas of Eswatini</p> <p>Study dates: September 2015 – August 2017</p> <p>Baseline annual parasite incidence: 5.2 per 1,000 from 2012–2015</p> <p>Study design: Cluster-randomized trial comparing RDA to RACD</p> <p>Unit of randomization: Locality</p> <p>Total number of clusters (total): 77</p> <p>Clusters in RACD arm: 38</p> <p>Total population in RACD arm: 2,752 (note that the population only includes the ‘at-risk’ population (part of the enumeration area within the locality that had incident cases during the trial))</p> <p>Total population in RDA arm: 2,680</p> <p><i>Note that the trial considered the intervention arm to be RDA, with RACD as the comparison arm; for this review we consider RACD to be the intervention arm and RDA the comparison. RDA was largely conducted by the study staff whereas RACD relied more on the Ministry of Health routine response.</i></p>
---------	---

Participants	<p>Number of RACD ‘events’: 46 (covering 53 cases (of 99 reported) in 22 localities)</p> <p>Number of household members/neighbors tested: 1,455</p> <p>Percent tested of total targeted: 1,455 /1,855 = 78.4%</p> <p>Number of household members/neighbors positive: 5</p> <p>Number of household members/neighbors treated: 5 (referred for treatment)</p>
Interventions	<p><u>Intervention:</u></p> <p>Drug(s) used for RACD: Artemether-lumefantrine</p> <p>Index case detection: Through passive surveillance at health facilities and confirmed by RDT or microscopy</p> <p>Area targeted around index case: Households within a 500-meter radius of index case; those testing positive by RDT were referred to the nearest health facility for treatment.</p> <p><u>Comparison:</u></p> <p>Type: RDA with dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine targeting households within a 200-meter radius</p> <p><u>Co-interventions:</u> Case management, pre-season IRS</p>
Outcomes	<p><u>Incidence of clinical cases:</u></p> <p>Measurement: Routine data on malaria cases diagnosed by microscopy and RDT at health facilities. Only local cases included in outcome (although the authors did an analysis with all cases as well).</p> <p>Time points: Jan 2017 – December 2017</p> <p>Analysis: Negative binomial regression with an offset for cluster population size. The first index case in each cluster was not included to allow time for the intervention to have an effect. Adjusted model included covariates associated with an outcome (not pre-specified), which was incidence of local cases in 2014 – 2015.</p> <p><u>Adverse events:</u></p> <p>For those in the RACD arm referred to facilities to take AL, there was not systematic counseling on AE reporting. In the RDA arm, there was a study nurse on call 24 hours per day, 7 days per week and also active pharmacovigilance in the community. AEs occurred in 68 individuals in the RDA arm, mostly headache, nausea/vomiting, and abdominal pain; 54 (80%) were mild and 14 (21%) were moderate. Counseling on AE reporting occurred during administration of dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine to those receiving RDA.</p>

Risk of bias

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Randomization process	Some concerns	Baseline imbalances due to inclusion of only clusters with an index case
Recruitment of participants into clusters	Low risk	Similar participation rates in both arms of the trial
Deviations from intended interventions	Some concerns	20 RACD interventions delivered in RDA arm (14 clusters); 5 RDA interventions delivered in RACD arm
Missing outcome data (clinical malaria incidence)	Low risk	No reason to believe there was differential missingness by study arm
Missing outcome data (adverse events)	High risk	Adverse events reported only from RDA arm
Measurement of outcome (clinical malaria incidence)	Low risk	Routine diagnosis at health facilities; unlikely that diagnosis affected by knowledge of study arm
Measurement of outcome (adverse events)	High risk	Adverse events reported only from RDA arm
Selection of reported result (clinical malaria incidence)	Low risk	Pre-specified outcome
Selection of reported result (adverse events)	Low risk	Pre-specified outcome

Non-randomized studies

Fortouna 2016

Methods	<p>Location: Acrelandia, Acre State, Amazonia, Brazil</p> <p>Study dates: January – July 2013</p> <p>Baseline annual parasite incidence: 5 per 1,000 in 2012; <i>P. vivax</i> accounts for 84% cases in the area</p> <p>Study design: Non-randomized before-and-after study</p> <p>Population in RACD area: 14,120</p> <p><i>Note: Passively-detected index cases triggered an RACD response with household members and neighbors within a defined radius <u>plus</u> 5 randomly selected control households residing in same locality but at least 5 km from the index case. All index case, neighboring and control households were followed up at 30, 60, 90, and 180 days and all household members tested for parasitemia.</i></p>
Participants	<p>Number of RACD 'events': 41 (all <i>P. vivax</i>)</p> <p>Number of household members/neighbors tested: 878 from index/neighboring households; 841 from control households</p> <p>Percent tested of total targeted: N/A</p>

	<p>Number of household members/neighbors positive (on Day 0): 17 of 835 (2.0%) by microscopy; 59 of 812 (7.2%) by PCR</p> <p>Number of household members/neighbors treated: 5 (referred for treatment): 17 on Day 0</p> <p><i>Note that there was only 1 positive microscopy test among 634 (0.2%) control households tested on Day 0 by microscopy and 35 of 631 (5.5%) positive by PCR on Day 0.</i></p>
Interventions	<p><u>Intervention:</u></p> <p>Drug(s) used for RACD: Chloroquine (total dose: 25 mg/kg over 3 days) and primaquine (0.5 mg/kg/day for 7 days).</p> <p>Index case detection: Through passive surveillance at health facilities and confirmed microscopy</p> <p>Area targeted around index case: 5 nearest houses within a radius of up to 3 km</p> <p>Detection of positives around index case: Thick smear microscopy (PCR also done but PCR positive/microscopy negative were not treated)</p> <p><u>Co-interventions:</u> Selective IRS implemented in early 2008, widespread distribution of LLINs since 2010</p>
Outcomes	<p><u>Prevalence of parasitemia among those receiving the intervention:</u></p> <p>Measurement: Thick smear microscopy and PCR</p> <p>Time points: On Day 0 (initial RACD), Day 30, Day 60, and Day 180</p> <p>Details: Diagnostics were done at intervention (index case and neighbor) households as well as control households during the four time points of the study. Participants were treated if they were microscopy positive.</p>

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Application of appropriate eligibility criteria	Low risk	Clear criteria were specified for control households (same locality, >5 kilometers from index case)
Flawed measurement in the exposure (i.e. intervention)	Low risk	Since the outcome is only among receiving the intervention, this domain is less relevant
Flawed measurement in the outcome	Low risk	Unlikely that those doing microscopy or PCR in the lab were aware of participant's status
Failure to adequately control for confounding	Low risk	Control households were included in measurement at baseline and all follow-up time points
Incomplete follow-up (loss that could introduce bias)	Low risk	There was equally good follow-up over time in the RACD and the control households

Downgrade from low to very low?	No	
---------------------------------	----	--

Searle 2020

Methods	<p>Location: Macha Hospital, Choma district, Southern Province, Zambia</p> <p>Study dates: March 2016 – March 2018</p> <p>Baseline annual parasite incidence: 1% PfPR in 2013</p> <p>Study design: Uncontrolled before-and-after study</p> <p>Population in RACD area: 14,120</p> <p><i>Note: Passively-detected index cases triggered an RACD response with household members and neighbors within 250 meters; these households with an RACD response on Day 0 were followed up at Day 30 and Day 90 and residents tested at each time point.</i></p>
Participants	<p>Number of RACD ‘events’: 84 index cases with Day 0 visit</p> <p>Number of household members/neighbors tested: 2,215 on Day 0 (676 from index households, 675 from neighbor households within 140 meters, and 864 within neighbor households within 141–250 meters)</p> <p>Percent tested of total targeted: N/A</p> <p>Number of household members/neighbors positive (on Day 0): 26 (1.2%) of 225 by RDT on Day 0; 83 (3.7%) of by PCR (Pf only) on Day 0</p> <p>Number of household members/neighbors treated: N/A</p>
Interventions	<p><u>Intervention:</u></p> <p>Drug(s) used for RACD: Artemether-lumefantrine</p> <p>Index case detection: Through passive surveillance at health facilities</p> <p>Area targeted around index case: 250 meters (increased from 140 in routine RACD response)</p> <p>Detection of positives around index case: RDT (HRP2)</p> <p><u>Co-interventions:</u> ITNs</p>
Outcomes	<p><u>Prevalence of parasitemia among those receiving the intervention:</u></p> <p>Measurement: Thick smear microscopy and PCR</p> <p>Time points: On Day 0 (initial RACD), Day 30, and Day 90</p> <p>Details: Diagnostics were done at intervention (index case and neighbor) households during the three time points of the study. Participants were treated if they were RDT positive.</p>

Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Application of appropriate eligibility criteria	Low risk	The RACD strategy had been carried out previously by community health workers who had experience in identifying cases for RACD
Flawed measurement in the exposure (i.e. intervention)	Low risk	Since the outcome is only among receiving the intervention, this domain is less relevant
Flawed measurement in the outcome	Some concerns	It is possible (but unlikely) that those doing RDTs or PCR in the lab were aware that all these participants received RACD
Failure to adequately control for confounding	High risk	There was no comparison group leaving this study very vulnerable to secular trends
Incomplete follow-up (loss that could introduce bias)	Low risk	High rates of follow-up at two later time points
Downgrade from low to very low?	Yes	Lack of comparison group

References

1. Cotter C, Sturrock HJ, Hsiang MS, Liu J, Phillips AA, Hwang J, et al. The changing epidemiology of malaria elimination: new strategies for new challenges. *Lancet*. 2013;382(9895):900-11.
2. Stresman G, Whittaker C, Slater HC, Bousema T, Cook J. Quantifying Plasmodium falciparum infections clustering within households to inform household-based intervention strategies for malaria control programs: An observational study and meta-analysis from 41 malaria-endemic countries. *PLoS Med*. 2020;17(10):e1003370.
3. Cao J, Sturrock HJ, Cotter C, Zhou S, Zhou H, Liu Y, et al. Communicating and monitoring surveillance and response activities for malaria elimination: China's "1-3-7" strategy. *PLoS Med*. 2014;11(5):e1001642.
4. van der Horst T, Al-Mafazy AW, Fakhri BS, Stuck L, Ali A, Yukich J, et al. Operational Coverage and Timeliness of Reactive Case Detection for Malaria Elimination in Zanzibar, Tanzania. *Am J Trop Med Hyg*. 2020;102(2):298-306.
5. Bansil P, Yeshiwondim AK, Guinovart C, Serda B, Scott C, Tesfay BH, et al. Malaria case investigation with reactive focal testing and treatment: operational feasibility and lessons learned from low and moderate transmission areas in Amhara Region, Ethiopia. *Malar J*. 2018;17(1):449.
6. Zemene E, Koepfli C, Tiruneh A, Yeshiwondim AK, Seyoum D, Lee MC, et al. Detection of foci of residual malaria transmission through reactive case detection in Ethiopia. *Malar J*. 2018;17(1):390.
7. Hsiang MS, Ntshalintshali N, Kang Dufour MS, Dlamini N, Nhlabathi N, Vilakati S, et al. Active Case Finding for Malaria: A 3-Year National Evaluation of Optimal Approaches to Detect Infections and Hotspots Through Reactive Case Detection in the Low-transmission Setting of Eswatini. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2020;70(7):1316-25.
8. Zelman BW, Baral R, Zarlinda I, Coutrier FN, Sanders KC, Cotter C, et al. Costs and cost-effectiveness of malaria reactive case detection using loop-mediated isothermal amplification compared to microscopy in the low transmission setting of Aceh Province, Indonesia. *Malar J*. 2018;17(1):220.
9. Stuck L, Fakhri BS, Al-Mafazy AH, Hofmann NE, Holzschuh A, Grossenbacher B, et al. Malaria infection prevalence and sensitivity of reactive case detection in Zanzibar. *Int J Infect Dis*. 2020;97:337-46.
10. van Eijk AM, Ramanathapuram L, Sutton PL, Kanagaraj D, Sri Lakshmi Priya G, Ravishankaran S, et al. What is the value of reactive case detection in malaria control? A case-study in India and a systematic review. *Malar J*. 2016;15:67.
11. Sterne JAC, Savovic J, Page MJ, Elbers RG, Blencowe NS, Boutron I, et al. RoB 2: a revised tool for assessing risk of bias in randomised trials. *BMJ*. 2019;366:l4898.
12. Higgins J, Savovic J, Page MJ, Elbers RG, Sterne J. Assessing risk of bias in a randomized trial. *Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions* Cochrane; 2020.
13. Guyatt GH, Oxman AD, Vist G, Kunz R, Brozek J, Alonso-Coello P, et al. GRADE guidelines: 4. Rating the quality of evidence--study limitations (risk of bias). *J Clin Epidemiol*. 2011;64(4):407-15.
14. Guyatt G, Oxman AD, Akl EA, Kunz R, Vist G, Brozek J, et al. GRADE guidelines: 1. Introduction- GRADE evidence profiles and summary of findings tables. *J Clin Epidemiol*. 2011;64(4):383-94.
15. Balshem H, Helfand M, Schunemann HJ, Oxman AD, Kunz R, Brozek J, et al. GRADE guidelines: 3. Rating the quality of evidence. *J Clin Epidemiol*. 2011;64(4):401-6.
16. Bridges D, Miller J, Chalwa V, Moonga H, Hamainza B, Steketee R, et al. Serological evaluations of malaria in the cluster randomized community-led responses for elimination (CoRE) trial. [Not yet published]2021.
17. Hsiang MS, Ntuku H, Roberts KW, Dufour MK, Whittemore B, Tambo M, et al. Effectiveness of reactive focal mass drug administration and reactive focal vector control to reduce malaria transmission

in the low malaria-endemic setting of Namibia: a cluster-randomised controlled, open-label, two-by-two factorial design trial. *Lancet*. 2020;395(10233):1361-73.

18. Vilakati S, Mngadi N, Benjamin-Chung J, Dlamini N, Dufour MK, Whittemore B, et al. Effectiveness and safety of reactive focal mass drug administration (rfMDA) using dihydroartemisinin-piperazine to reduce malaria transmission in the very low-endemic setting of Eswatini: a pragmatic cluster randomised controlled trial. *BMJ Glob Health*. 2021;6(6).
19. Searle KM, Katowa B, Musonda M, Pringle JC, Hamapumbu H, Matoba J, et al. Sustained Malaria Transmission despite Reactive Screen-and-Treat in a Low-Transmission Area of Southern Zambia. *Am J Trop Med Hyg*. 2020.
20. Fontoura PS, Finco BF, Lima NF, de Carvalho JF, Jr., Vinetz JM, Castro MC, et al. Reactive Case Detection for Plasmodium vivax Malaria Elimination in Rural Amazonia. *PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases* [electronic resource]. 2016;10(12):e0005221.
21. Getachew A, Yeshiwondim A, Bansil P, Serda B, Tesfay B, Agmas A, et al. Reactive case detection for malaria in amhara national Regional State, Ethiopia: descriptive and impact evaluation analysis. *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*. 2017;97 (5 Supplement 1):412.
22. Reiker T, Chitnis N, Smith T. Modelling reactive case detection strategies for interrupting transmission of Plasmodium falciparum malaria. *Malaria Journal*. 2019;18(1):259.
23. Hsiang MS, Ntshalintshali N, Kang Dufour MS, Dlamini N, Nhlabathi N, Vilakati S, et al. Active Case Finding for Malaria: A 3-Year National Evaluation of Optimal Approaches to Detect Infections and Hotspots Through Reactive Case Detection in the Low-transmission Setting of Eswatini. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*. 2020;70(7):1316-25.
24. Bekolo CE, Williams TD. Adding proactive and reactive case detection into the integrated community case management system to optimise diagnosis and treatment of malaria in a high transmission setting of Cameroon: an observational quality improvement study. *BMJ Open*. 2019;9(6):e026678.
25. Roberts KW, Smith Gueye C, Baltzell K, Ntuku H, McCreesh P, Maglior A, et al. Community acceptance of reactive focal mass drug administration and reactive focal vector control using indoor residual spraying, a mixed-methods study in Zambezi region, Namibia. *Malar J*. 2021;20(1):162.
26. Littrell M, Sow GD, Ngom A, Ba M, Mboup BM, Dieye Y, et al. Case investigation and reactive case detection for malaria elimination in northern Senegal. *Malaria Journal*. 2013;12:331.
27. Lohfeld L, Kangombe-Ngwenya T, Winters AM, Chisha Z, Hamainza B, Kamuliwo M, et al. A qualitative review of implementer perceptions of the national community-level malaria surveillance system in Southern Province, Zambia. *Malaria Journal*. 2016;15(1):400.
28. Kheang ST, Sovannaroth S, Barat LM, Dysoley L, Kapella BK, Po L, et al. Malaria elimination using the 1-3-7 approach: lessons from Sampov Loun, Cambodia. *BMC Public Health*. 2020;20(1):544.
29. Hustedt J, Canavati SE, Rang C, Ashton RA, Khim N, Berne L, et al. Reactive case-detection of malaria in Pailin Province, Western Cambodia: lessons from a year-long evaluation in a pre-elimination setting. *Malar J*. 2016;15:132.
30. Lu G, Liu Y, Beiersmann C, Feng Y, Cao J, Muller O. Challenges in and lessons learned during the implementation of the 1-3-7 malaria surveillance and response strategy in China: a qualitative study. *Infect Dis Poverty*. 2016;5(1):94.
31. Lu G, Liu Y, Beiersmann C, Feng Y, Cao J, Muller O. Challenges of foci investigation in malaria elimination program in China: A qualitative study. *European Journal of Epidemiology*. 2016;31 (Supplement 1):S121-S2.
32. Wang D, Cotter C, Sun X, Bennett A, Gosling RD, Xiao N. Adapting the local response for malaria elimination through evaluation of the 1-3-7 system performance in the China-Myanmar border region. *Malaria Journal*. 2017;16(1):54.

33. van Eijk AM, Ramanathapuram L, Sutton PL, Kanagaraj D, Sri Lakshmi Priya G, Ravishankaran S, et al. What is the value of reactive case detection in malaria control? A case-study in India and a systematic review. *Malaria Journal*. 2016;15:67.
34. Chihanga S, Haque U, Chanda E, Mosweunyane T, Moakofhi K, Jibril HB, et al. Malaria elimination in Botswana, 2012-2014: achievements and challenges. *Parasit Vectors*. 2016;9:99.
35. Stuck L, Fasih BS, Al-Mafazy AH, Hofmann NE, Holzschuh A, Grossenbacher B, et al. Malaria infection prevalence and sensitivity of reactive case detection in Zanzibar. *International Journal of Infectious Diseases*. 2020;97:337-46.
36. Cotter C, Sudathip P, Herdiana H, Cao Y, Liu Y, Luo A, et al. Piloting a programme tool to evaluate malaria case investigation and reactive case detection activities: results from 3 settings in the Asia Pacific. *Malaria Journal*. 2017;16(1):347.
37. Zelman BW, Baral R, Zarlinda I, Coutrier FN, Sanders KC, Cotter C, et al. Costs and cost-effectiveness of malaria reactive case detection using loop-mediated isothermal amplification compared to microscopy in the low transmission setting of Aceh Province, Indonesia. *Malaria Journal*. 2018;17(1):220.
38. Conner RO, Dieye Y, Hainsworth M, Tall A, Cisse B, Faye F, et al. Correction to: Mass testing and treatment for malaria followed by weekly fever screening, testing and treatment in Northern Senegal: feasibility, cost and impact. *Malar J*. 2020;19(1):443.
39. Galactionova K, Velarde M, Silumbe K, Miller J, McDonnell A, Aguas R, et al. Costing malaria interventions from pilots to elimination programmes. *Malaria Journal*. 2020;19(1):332.
40. Larson BA, Ngoma T, Silumbe K, Rutagwera MR, Hamainza B, Winters AM, et al. A framework for evaluating the costs of malaria elimination interventions: an application to reactive case detection in Southern Province of Zambia, 2014. *Malaria Journal*. 2016;15(1):408.
41. Gerardin J, Bever CA, Bridenbecker D, Hamainza B, Silumbe K, Miller JM, et al. Effectiveness of reactive case detection for malaria elimination in three archetypical transmission settings: a modelling study. *Malaria Journal*. 2017;16(1):248.
42. WHO handbook for guideline development 2014. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/145714>.
43. Booth A, Moore G, Flemming K, Garside R, Rollins N, Tuncalp O, et al. Taking account of context in systematic reviews and guidelines considering a complexity perspective. *BMJ Glob Health*. 2019;4(Suppl 1):e000840.
44. Wangdi K, Banwell C, Gatton ML, Kelly GC, Namgay R, Clements AC. Development and evaluation of a spatial decision support system for malaria elimination in Bhutan. *Malaria Journal*. 2016;15:180.
45. Herdiana H, Cotter C, Coutrier FN, Zarlinda I, Zelman BW, Tirta YK, et al. Malaria risk factor assessment using active and passive surveillance data from Aceh Besar, Indonesia, a low endemic, malaria elimination setting with *Plasmodium knowlesi*, *Plasmodium vivax*, and *Plasmodium falciparum*. *Malaria Journal*. 2016;15:468.
46. Larsen DA, Chisha Z, Winters B, Mwanza M, Kamuliwo M, Mbwili C, et al. Malaria surveillance in low-transmission areas of Zambia using reactive case detection. *Malaria Journal*. 2015;14:465.
47. Van Der Horst T, Al-Mafazy AW, Fasih BS, Stuck L, Ali A, Yukich J, et al. Operational coverage and timeliness of reactive case detection for malaria elimination in Zanzibar, Tanzania. *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*. 2020;102(2):298-306.
48. Searle KM, Hamapumbu H, Lubinda J, Shields TM, Pinchoff J, Kobayashi T, et al. Evaluation of the operational challenges in implementing reactive screen-and-treat and implications of reactive case detection strategies for malaria elimination in a region of low transmission in southern Zambia. *Malaria Journal*. 2016;15(1):412.

49. Wangdi K, Banwell C, Gatton ML, Kelly GC, Namgay R, Clements AC. Development and evaluation of a spatial decision support system for malaria elimination in Bhutan. *Malar J.* 2016;15:180.
50. Hustedt J, Canavati SE, Rang C, Ashton RA, Khim N, Berne L, et al. Reactive case-detection of malaria in Pailin Province, Western Cambodia: lessons from a year-long evaluation in a pre-elimination setting. *Malaria Journal.* 2016;15:132.
51. Smith Gueye C, Sanders KC, Galappaththy GNL, Rundi C, Tobgay T, Sovannaroeth S, et al. Active case detection for malaria elimination: a survey among Asia Pacific countries. *Malaria Journal.* 2013;12(1):358.
52. Bansil P, Yeshiwondim AK, Guinovart C, Serda B, Scott C, Tesfay BH, et al. Malaria case investigation with reactive focal testing and treatment: operational feasibility and lessons learned from low and moderate transmission areas in Amhara Region, Ethiopia. *Malaria Journal.* 2018;17(1):449.
53. Conner RO, Dieye Y, Hainsworth M, Tall A, Cisse B, Faye F, et al. Mass testing and treatment for malaria followed by weekly fever screening, testing and treatment in Northern Senegal: feasibility, cost and impact. *Malar J.* 2020;19(1):252.
54. Rogawski ET, Congpuong K, Sudathip P, Satimai W, Sug-aram R, Aruncharus S, et al. Active case detection with pooled real-time PCR to eliminate malaria in Trat province, Thailand. *Am J Trop Med Hyg.* 2012;86(5):789-91.
55. Herdiana H, Cotter C, Coutrier F, Tirta YK, Zarlinda I, Zelman BW, et al. Use of active and passive surveillance to determine the risk factors for malaria infection in aceh besar, indonesia, a low-endemic, multi-species setting (plasmodium knowlesi, P. vivax, and P. falciparum infection) aiming for malaria elimination. *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene.* 2016;95 (5 Supplement 1):280.

Appendix 1: Definitions of outcomes and contextual factors

- 1) Incidence of malaria infection
- 2) Prevalence of malaria infection
- 3) Elimination (defined as 0 indigenous or local cases for a period during the peak transmission season)
- 4) Incidence of clinical malaria or number of indigenous malaria cases

Measured among those targeted by the intervention

- 5) Adverse events
- 6) Prevalence of infection

OUTCOMES	
<i>Measured at community level</i>	
1) Incidence of malaria infection	Number of cases of malaria identified through active surveillance, divided by the product of the population and the time under observation
2) Prevalence of malaria infection	Number of people with malaria parasitemia (diagnostically confirmed) divided by the number tested, among a given population

3) Elimination (defined as 0 indigenous or local cases for a period during the peak transmission season)	Zero measured indigenous or local cases for a period during the peak transmission season
4) Incidence of clinical malaria or number of indigenous malaria cases	Number of local (indigenous) malaria cases among a certain population over a given time period; if measured by passive case detection, typically expressed as the number of cases divided by the population (for the time period specified); if measured in an incidence cohort, typically expressed as the number of cases divided by person-time
<i>Among those receiving the intervention</i>	
5) Adverse events	Known adverse drug events for the given antimalarial medication used
6) Prevalence of infection	Number of people with malaria parasitemia (diagnostically confirmed) divided by the number tested, among the population (or a subset) receiving RACD
CONTEXTUAL FACTORS	
Values and preferences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The values and preferences of the individuals and populations affected by the recommendation with respect to the outcomes associated with the intervention
Acceptability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Extent to which those benefiting from the intervention as well as other relevant stakeholder groups consider the intervention to be appropriate (based on anticipated or experienced cognitive and emotional responses to the intervention) Willingness to participate in the intervention
Health equity, equality and non-discrimination	<p>Extent to which the intervention:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Benefits all populations Does not discriminate against anyone on the basis of sex, age, ethnicity, culture, language, sexual orientation or gender identity, disability status, education, socioeconomic status, residence or any other characteristic. <i>Note:</i> This could include whether the benefits and harms are equally distributed and whether the intervention is equally affordable and accessible to all
Financial and economic considerations:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Costs Resource intensiveness Overall economic impact Cost-benefit <i>Note:</i> a specific consideration for RACD will be the efficiency, or “yield” of RACD, e.g., the number of cases needed to be screened around the index case to yield one additional positive case
Feasibility and health system considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Legal barriers to implementation Interaction with existing health system

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Need for and use of the existing health workforce (e.g., to conduct intervention) or other resources• Programmatic considerations• <i>Note:</i> this includes the ability to reach all targeted households/household members in a timely manner; adherence to drug completion among those given antimalarials
--	---

Appendix 2: Search terms and results

Search Query: Reactive strategies include either: reactive case detection (testing and treating those positive) around an index case (presenting to health facilities or community health workers), drug administration (without testing) for households around an index case

Search Strategy:

Database	Strategy	Run Date	Records
Medline (OVID) 1946-	Malaria* AND (((screen* ADJ5 treat*) OR (test* ADJ5 treat*)) AND (focal OR foci OR index OR contact*)) OR (reactive* ADJ5 detect*) OR (passive* ADJ5 detect*) OR (reactive* ADJ5 administration) OR (reactive* ADJ5 screen*) OR (reactive* ADJ5 test*) OR (reactive* ADJ5 treat*) OR (focal ADJ5 administration) OR (foci ADJ5 administration) OR (focal ADJ5 MDA) OR (foci ADJ5 MDA)	11/16/2020	416
Embase (OVID) 1988-	Malaria* AND (((screen* ADJ5 treat*) OR (test* ADJ5 treat*)) AND (focal OR foci OR index OR contact*)) OR (reactive* ADJ5 detect*) OR (passive* ADJ5 detect*) OR (reactive* ADJ5 administration) OR (reactive* ADJ5 screen*) OR (reactive* ADJ5 test*) OR (reactive* ADJ5 treat*) OR (focal ADJ5 administration) OR (foci ADJ5 administration) OR (focal ADJ5 MDA) OR (foci ADJ5 MDA) NOT pubmed/medline	11/16/2020	715 -387 duplicates =328 unique items
Global Health (OVID) 1910_	Malaria* AND (((screen* ADJ5 treat*) OR (test* ADJ5 treat*)) AND (focal OR foci OR index OR contact*)) OR (reactive* ADJ5 detect*) OR (passive* ADJ5 detect*) OR (reactive* ADJ5 administration) OR (reactive* ADJ5 screen*) OR (reactive* ADJ5 test*) OR (reactive* ADJ5 treat*) OR (focal ADJ5 administration) OR (foci ADJ5 administration) OR (focal ADJ5 MDA) OR (foci ADJ5 MDA)	11/16/2020	451 -334 duplicates =117 unique items
Cochrane Library	Malaria*:ti,ab AND ((((screen* NEAR/5 treat*) OR (test* NEAR/5 treat*)) AND (focal OR foci OR index OR contact*)) OR (reactive* NEAR/5 detect*) OR (passive* NEAR/5 detect*) OR (reactive* NEAR/5 administration) OR (reactive* NEAR/5 screen*) OR (reactive* NEAR/5 test*) OR (reactive* NEAR/5 treat*) OR (focal NEAR/5 administration) OR (foci NEAR/5 administration) OR (focal NEAR/5 MDA) OR (foci NEAR/5 MDA)):ti,ab	11/16/2020	161 -105 duplicates =56 unique items

CINAHL (EbscoHost)	Malaria* AND (((screen* N5 treat*) OR (test* N5 treat*)) AND (focal OR foci OR index OR contact*)) OR (reactive* N5 detect*) OR (passive* N5 detect*) OR (reactive* N5 administration) OR (reactive* N5 screen*) OR (reactive* N5 test*) OR (reactive* N5 treat*) OR (focal N5 administration) OR (foci N5 administration) OR (focal N5 MDA) OR (foci N5 MDA))	11/16/2020	75 -57 duplicates =18 unique items
Scopus	TITLE-ABS-KEY(Malaria*) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY((((screen* W/5 treat*) OR (test* W/5 treat*)) AND (focal OR foci OR index OR contact*)) OR (reactive* W/5 detect*) OR (passive* W/5 detect*) OR (reactive* W/5 administration) OR (reactive* W/5 screen*) OR (reactive* W/5 test*) OR (reactive* W/5 treat*) OR (focal W/5 administration) OR (foci W/5 administration) OR (focal W/5 MDA) OR (foci W/5 MDA))	11/16/2020	552 -445 duplicates =107 unique items
Clinicaltrials.gov	Malaria reactive case detection completed OR focal mass drug administration OR foci mass drug administration OR focal MDA OR foci MDA Completed Studies malaria	11/16/2020	6 -1 duplicates =5 unique items
Global Index Medicus	Malaria* AND ((screen* OR test*) AND (focal OR foci OR index OR contact*)) OR (reactive* AND detect*) OR (passive* AND detect*) OR (reactive* AND administration) OR (reactive* AND screen*) OR (reactive* AND test*) OR (reactive* AND treat*) OR (focal AND administration) OR (foci AND administration) OR (focal AND MDA) OR (foci AND MDA)	11/16/2020	313 -36 duplicates =277 unique items

Notes: Duplicates were identified using the Endnote automated "find duplicates" function with preference set to match on title, author and year, and removed from your Endnote library. There will likely be additional duplicates found that Endnote was unable to detect.

Appendix 3: Alternative forest plots for prevalence of parasitemia and incidence of confirmed malaria (with correct lower bound for 95% CI for Hsiang 2020(17))

Figure 7: Forest plot of comparison: RDA versus no RDA/RACD on parasitemia prevalence

Footnotes

- The 95% CI lower limit presented here is lower than in the published paper (odds ratio = 1.85, 95% CI: **0.96**, 20.00). Effect size from (non-linear) marginal effect post-estimation from generalized estimating equations (GEE) model using a logit function adjusted for reactive IRS, the interaction between reactive IRS and RDA, 2016 incidence of local cases, index case level and target population coverage for RDA or RACD, response time, and co-interventions by Namibia MoH. Unadjusted effect size (from post-estimation marginal effect of RDA from GEE model using a logit function adjusted for reactive IRS, the interaction between reactive IRS and RDA but no other covariates):0.95 (95% CI: 0.48, 33.3).

Figure 8: Forest plot of comparison: RDA versus no RDA/RACD on confirmed malaria incidence

Footnotes

- Negative binomial analysis of monthly facility cases (random intercept for facility); adjusted for previous month's cases, NDVI, precipitation, altitude, night-time light, number RDTs done each month, and seasonality (fourier term). Unadjusted estimate: 0.93 (0.77, 2.00).
- The 95% CI lower limit is lower here than in the published paper (1.41 (95% CI: **0.83**, 4.55); estimate from (non-linear) marginal effect post-estimation from a negative binomial model with offset for cluster-level person time; adjusted for reactive vector control, interaction between RDA and reactive vector control, 2016 incidence of local cases, index case level and target population coverage for RACD or RDA, response time, and co-interventions by Namibia Ministry of Health. Unadjusted marginal effects from post-estimation (from unadjusted negative binomial model with terms for RACD, reactive IRS, and the interaction between the two, with offset for cluster-level person time): 1.22 (0.73, 3.85).
- Negative binomial regression model of local cases with offset for person-time and adjusted for baseline (2014-2015) incidence of local cases. Unadjusted estimate: 0.94 (95% CI: 0.51, 1.75).

Appendix 4: Detailed synthesis of contextual factors related to RACD

Introduction

The extent to which systematic reviews and guidelines of complex interventions, like reactive case detection (RACD), consider and report contextual factors that determine the direction and strength of a recommendation in public health policy formulations(42) is limited by inadequate information on context in included primary studies(43). To facilitate a structured process of reflection and discussion in a problem-specific and context-specific manner, the WHO in its new WHO-INTEGRATE (INTEGRATE Evidence) evidence to decision framework 1.0, recommends reporting and consideration of six substantive criteria—balance of health benefits and harms, human rights and sociocultural acceptability, health equity, equality and non-discrimination, societal implications, financial and economic considerations, and feasibility and health system considerations—and the meta-criterion quality of evidence, applicable to all the six criteria. The first criteria balance of health benefits and harms was the primary objective of our systematic reviews and is reported in the main body of this report. In this study, we report on contextual factors, that align with these criteria that are relevant for RACD guideline development process.

We included 28 studies, 10 from the Asia-Pacific (AP) region and 18 from sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), to assess for five categories of contextual factors (**Table 6**). Data was not available for the following two categories of contextual factors: values and preferences, and health equity. We abstracted data for other three categories of contextual factors which are discussed below.

Acceptability

Sociocultural acceptability

Community and health care worker's acceptability data were abstracted from 4 studies from Cameroon(24), Namibia(25), Senegal(26), and Zambia(27).(**Table 7**)

Community acceptance of RACD was high (refusal rate 2% or lower). In Namibia, some "hesitation/resistance" during pre-trial was reported but community engagement and sensitization appear to have helped participation. Similarly, in Senegal the high RACD participation has been attributed to advanced cascade sensitization, making follow-up appointments for absent members, and conducting return visits to the compound the same or next day. Lack of community confidence in community health care workers (CHWs) ability to address diseases other than malaria and community unwillingness to visit CHWs for malaria testing were reported from Zambia (27).

Health Care Worker Acceptability

There were no studies reporting data directly on health care workers' (HCWs) acceptance of RACD. Related information was abstracted from two studies. In Zambia(27), CHWs reported lack of motivation to conduct RACD, which was in part linked to CHWs feeling their community service went unrecognized. In Cameroon, CHWs thought conducting only a 1day visit per week to health facilities and only to households of index cases was more productive(24). The lack of stipend or financial support was the biggest problem noted by CHWs who were volunteers.(27)

Feasibility and health systems consideration

We abstracted feasibility and health systems considerations data from 17 studies (**Table 6**), 7 from SSA and 8 from AP region. Barriers and major challenges to RACD and suggestions for addressing them are thematically stratified along the three different steps of RACD. (**Table 8**).

Index case detection and notification

Index case notification from private health facilities is low and these cases are largely reported to be missed by RACD in Cambodia(28, 29) and Zanzibar(4) . Collaborating and engaging the private sector in malaria surveillance systems has been identified as critical, particularly in areas where many patients resort to private providers, facilities including drug shops, and pharmacies (4)

Within the public health sector, delayed presentation of malaria patients to health facilities, poor preparation of village clinics to participate in surveillance programmes, and the lack of adequate human resources and malaria RDTs have been reported as barriers and challenges to effective RACD(30).

Case investigation

Complexity of case investigation procedures and lack of standard operating procedures have been identified as barriers to effective case investigation (30). Case classification (imported v. indigenous) difficulty has also been reported due to incomplete travel histories(30, 31).

During peak malaria transmission seasons in Zambia, the proportion of case investigations conducted were lower than other times mainly due CHWs being overwhelmed by patient volume as well as inadequate malaria rapid diagnostic test. To overcome these barriers, authors have suggested that the programme would benefit from additional CHWs or suspension of RACD.

Reactive case detection

Barriers to timely follow-up during RACD have been reported due to difficulty accessing mountainous terrains(32), flooded areas(27), and border areas with highly mobile populations(32). . To overcome barriers posed by flooding during rainy season, study authors from Zambia recommend that CHWs, particularly who serve flood-prone areas, should be provided with rain gear and access to boats (27).

Another barrier to effective RACD was the large numbers of households to screen, particularly in high density areas of the Asia Pacific regions(33).

Incomplete case investigation forms limit follow-up(34), and lack of household-level listing of all individuals in the RACD area means that those conducting RACD do not always know which households to include in RACD. Authors of a study conducted China, Indonesia, Thailand recommend that, “Programmes should consider including an indicator on total population to be screened during RACD, update routine data collection forms to include the total number of individuals living in each household they visit, and to store that information in a central location for future use and updating as necessary”(36). Imported cases pose a major challenge for RACD. District-level responses alone are unlikely to be ineffective in interrupting transmission when most malaria cases are imported from outside the district (28). Communication and surveillance linkages with other operational districts and their malaria response teams are necessary.

RACD buffer zones can sometimes extend beyond international borders, limiting adequate RACD activities(44). Strengthened cross-border collaborations are needed to ensure adequate coverage of households across borders, migrant and mobile populations(28).

A key barrier in conducting effective RACD is malaria rapid diagnostic test (RDT) stockouts which prevented testing around index cases(23) as well as the low sensitivity of RDTs and the inability of *Plasmodium falciparum* specific RDTs to detect other species and low-density infections(30, 34, 35) . In Botswana, malaria microscopy was used as the gold standard for malaria diagnosis, so all RDT-positive malaria cases were re-examined by microscopy, ensuring high quality of malaria microscopy slides prepared by health center staff in these settings are challenging [14]. To overcome these challenges,

loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP) or other more sensitive diagnostics have been recommended(30, 35).

Lack of HCWs to conduct malaria activities and lack of surveillance officers at district level have been reported to result in inadequate supervision, case investigation and follow-up(36). Lack of motivation among HCWs to pursue case investigation and contact testing, particularly during weekends and public holidays has also been reported(28). Maintaining workforce motivation and providing consistent support, supervision and incentives have been recommended to overcome these challenges(27, 28).

Household coverage by RACD

The proportion of eligible households reached by RACD varies across different geographic locations (**Table 9**), with 49% of index case households investigated in Zanzibar to 100% in Jiangsu, China. Similarly, the proportion of households reached in a timely manner also varies across different locations, from about 20% in Zanzibar to 100% in China.

Adherence to antimalarials among those treated

Adherence to artemether-lumefantrine (AL) was reported from one study in Namibia which found nearly 100% adherence in 368 individuals who had their blister packs at follow-up pill counts. Among individuals without their blister packs (n=316), all but one reported full adherence to AL.

Financial and economic considerations

Financial and economic data were abstracted from nine studies from SSA and the AP region (Table 1).

Cost per person screened

The cost per person screened during RACD was reported from 3 countries (Table 5). The average cost of screening varies across different regions, with US \$5.21 in Thailand to US \$27.6 in Indonesia, where the general cost of screening one individual during RACD was \$11, with an additional microscopy cost of \$0.62 per person and \$16 per person for LAMP(37). In Senegal, the cost per person screened by RACD was US \$14.3 (38). In Thailand, 1:4 pooling of PCR samples, reduced the number of PCR reactions required from 191 to 67 (65%) without reducing the detection limit of the assay, which resulted in a cost of US \$ 1.25 per sample, savings about US \$155.

Other numerical information on costs

Costing models developed(39) based on experience of implementing partners, operational documents and costing studies from Ethiopia, Senegal, and Zambia, show the average annual financial cost per capita (total population of 360,000 based on 1 region, 3 districts, 20 HFCA each, 6000 population per HFCA) were \$1.07 for the first year of RACD, and \$0.65 per year for the next 5 years (USD, 2014) and the per capita economic cost was \$1.27 in first year of RACD, and \$0.75 per year for the next 5 years (USD, 2014).

Breakdown of cost components

RACD costs totals show variation between study areas ranging from \$3,469 in Indonesia to \$10,486 in Thailand for total personnel and \$257 (Indonesia) to \$13,969 (Thailand) for commodities, services and other costs(36). These variations in personnel, commodities, services, and other costs specific to case investigation and RACD activities reported are likely due to differences in programme structure and level of integration of malaria related activities into the broader healthcare system(36).

In Zambia, the mean annual cost of RACD per health facility catchment area (HFCA) was \$1177 (median = \$923, IQR \$651–\$1417)(40). The variation in costs was driven by the number of CHWs and passive cases detected. CHW-related costs and data review meetings accounted for the largest share of costs. RDTs and drugs accounted for less than 10% of total costs.

RACD cost components from Indonesia and Senegal are summarized in the table below. Personnel, training and capital costs are the top three cost component.

Number and composition of screening team

In Indonesia, the investigation team consisted of five people: a microscopist and surveillance officer from the primary health care center (PHC), two community health workers from the village (a midwife plus a village malaria worker or village leader), and the study field coordinator. Up to two return visits were conducted to maximize coverage of the target area(45)

In Zambia, the investigation team composition was different in urban and rural areas. In urban Lusaka, the team comprised of an environmental health technician, nurse and 2 CHWs while in rural areas a single CHW performed RACD(46).

Other information on resource intensiveness

Cost models based on studies from Ethiopia, Senegal, and Zambia show target search radius and per-diems paid to CHWs dominate intervention parameters. Increasing the search radius to 30 people, as seen in the Senegal pilot, and some of the health facility catchment areas (HFCAs) in Zambia, will increase cost of RACD to nearly 2 USD per capita(39).

In Indonesia(37), at 0.4% prevalence of infection, the cost per infection identified is \$,7070, and declines to \$1,767 when the prevalence is 1.6%. Cost declines begin to plateau thereafter.

In Zambia(40), community case management with RACD is transmission dependent and serves somewhat like an insurance role in an overall package of malaria elimination interventions; a certain set of costs are incurred even if a small number of households are visited by CHWs, which would be the case if few malaria cases were passively detected in the health facility or community. For example, from Table 5, if even 0 households were visited, average costs per HFCA would remain at about \$850 per 1000 population (although CHW labour time and costs for associated supplies, RDTs, drugs are eliminated etc.)

Table 6 Studies included for RACD contextual factors data abstraction

Country Region	Title	Lead author Year	Values	Acceptability	Equity	Costs	Feasibility
Ethiopia, Senegal, Zambia (Modeling study)	Costing malaria interventions from pilots to elimination programmes	Galactionova 2020	0	0	0	1	0
Asia Pacific	Piloting a programme tool to evaluate malaria case investigation and reactive case detection activities: results from 3 settings in the Asia Pacific	Cotter 2017	0	0	0	1	1
Asia Pacific	Active case detection for malaria elimination: a survey among Asia Pacific countries	SmithGueye 2013	0	0	0	0	1
Bhutan	Development and evaluation of a spatial decision support system for malaria elimination in Bhutan	Wangdi 2016	0	0	0	0	1
Botswana	Malaria elimination in Botswana, 2012-2014: achievements and challenges	Chihanga 2016	0	0	0	0	1
Cambodia	Reactive case-detection of malaria in Pailin Province, Western Cambodia: lessons from a year-long evaluation in a pre-elimination setting	Hustedt 2016	0	0	0	0	1
Cambodia	Malaria elimination using the 1-3-7 approach: lessons from Sampov Loun, Cambodia	Kheang 2020	0	0	0	0	1
Cameroon	Adding proactive and reactive case detection into the integrated community case management system to optimise diagnosis and treatment of malaria in a high transmission setting of Cameroon: an observational quality improvement study	Bekolo 2019	0	1	0	0	0
China	Challenges in and lessons learned during the implementation of the 1-3-7 malaria surveillance and response strategy in China: a qualitative study	Lu 2016	0	0	0	0	1
China-Myanmar	Adapting the local response for malaria elimination through evaluation of the 1-3-7 system performance in the China-Myanmar border region	Wang 2017	0	0	0	0	1
Eswatini	Active Case Finding for Malaria: A 3-Year National Evaluation of Optimal Approaches to Detect Infections and Hotspots Through Reactive Case Detection in the Low-transmission Setting of Eswatini	Hsiang 2020	0	0	0	0	1

Country Region	Title	Lead author Year	Values	Acceptability	Equity	Costs	Feasibility
Ethiopia	Malaria case investigation with reactive focal testing and treatment: operational feasibility and lessons learned from low and moderate transmission areas in Amhara Region, Ethiopia	Bansil 2018	0	0	0	0	1
India	What is the value of reactive case detection in malaria control? A case-study in India and a systematic review	vanEijk 2016	0	0	0	0	1
Indonesia	Malaria risk factor assessment using active and passive surveillance data from Aceh Besar, Indonesia, a low endemic, malaria elimination setting with Plasmodium knowlesi, Plasmodium vivax, and Plasmodium falciparum	Herdiana 2016	0	0	0	1	0
Indonesia	Costs and cost-effectiveness of malaria reactive case detection using loop-mediated isothermal amplification compared to microscopy in the low transmission setting of Aceh Province, Indonesia	Zelman 2018	0	0	0	1	0
Namibia	Effectiveness of reactive focal mass drug administration and reactive focal vector control to reduce malaria transmission in the low malaria-endemic setting of Namibia: a cluster-randomised controlled, open-label, two-by-two factorial design trial	Hsiang 2020	0	0	0	0	1
Namibia	Community acceptance of reactive focal mass drug administration and reactive focal vector control using indoor residual spraying, a mixed-methods study in Zambezi region, Namibia	Roberts 2021	0	1	0	0	0
Senegal	Scaling up malaria intervention "packages" in Senegal: using cost effectiveness data for improving allocative efficiency and programmatic decision-making	Faye 2018	0	0	0	1	0
Senegal	Mass testing and treatment for malaria followed by weekly fever screening, testing and treatment in Northern Senegal: feasibility, cost and impact	Conner 2020	0	0	0	1	0
Senegal	Case investigation and reactive case detection for malaria elimination in northern Senegal	Littrell 2013	0	1	0	0	0
Thailand	Active case detection with pooled real-time PCR to eliminate malaria in Trat province Thailand	Roawski 2012	0	0	0	1	0
Zambia	Evaluation of the operational challenges in implementing reactive screen-and-treat and implications of reactive case	Searle 2016	0	0	0	0	1

Country Region	Title	Lead author	Year	Values	Acceptability	Equity	Costs	Feasibility
Zambia	detection strategies for malaria elimination in a region of low transmission in southern Zambia A qualitative review of implementer perceptions of the national community-level malaria surveillance system in Southern Province, Zambia	Lohfeld	2016	0	1	0	0	1
Zambia	A framework for evaluating the costs of malaria elimination interventions: an application to reactive case detection in Southern Province of Zambia, 2014	Larson	2016	0	0	0	1	0
Zambia	Malaria surveillance in low-transmission areas of Zambia using reactive case detection	Larsen	2015	0	0	0	1	0
Zambia	Improving the efficiency of reactive case detection for malaria elimination in southern Zambia: a cross-sectional study	Bhondoekhan	2020	0	0	0	0	1
Zanzibar	Malaria infection prevalence and sensitivity of reactive case detection in Zanzibar	Stuck	2020	0	0	0	0	1
Zanzibar	Operational coverage and timeliness of reactive case detection for malaria elimination in Zanzibar, Tanzania	VanDerHorst	2020	0	0	0	0	1
Total				0	4	0	9	17

Table 7 Community and health care workers' acceptance to participate in RACD, in three countries in sub-Saharan countries

Country	Barriers/Challenges to acceptance	Solutions/reasons for success³	Refusal rate
<i>Community acceptance</i>			
Namibia(25)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Community members hesitation/resistance to RACD during pre-trial interviews. A few concerns (superstitions) about blood draws 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Community engagement and sensitization appears to have helped participation” The study team’s professionalism, and the respect shown for participants and local traditions were reported as critical for successful RACD implementation 	<p>Year 1: 0.34% (3/894)</p> <p>Year 2: 0.21% (10/4711)</p>
Senegal (26) (Richard Toll district)		<p>High participation was facilitated by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Advanced cascade sensitization whereby the health facility contacted the village health committee and requested that a committee member notify affected compounds on the evening prior to the investigation team visit Initial compound visits and booking appointments for follow-up with absent members; and return visits to the compound the same or next day. 	2%
Zambia(27)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of community confidence in CHWs’ ability to address diseases other than malaria Lack of community willingness to visit CHWs for malaria testing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide notifications to alert HH members when RACD would occur 	
<i>Health care workers’ acceptance</i>			
Zambia(27)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of motivation on the part of some CHWs linked to many feeling their community service went unrecognized. By far the biggest problem noted by CHWs was the lack of stipend or financial support for the volunteers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> None reported 	

³Suggestions are those provided in the articles reviewed

Table 8. Barriers, challenges, and solutions along the three steps of reactive case detection

Barriers/Challenges		Solutions⁴
Index case detection and notification		
Private Health Sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> RACD may not include passively detected cases at private health facilities (36) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engaging the private sector in malaria surveillance systems is critical, particularly in areas where many patients resort to private HFs, drug shops, or pharmacies (47) Collaborations with private providers is critical (28)
Public health sector		
Patient care seeking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Delayed presentation of malaria patients to clinics(31) 	
Inadequate preparation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Village clinics not part of malaria web-based reporting system(31) 	
Human Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited diagnostic skills and shortage of primary health care staff (31) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Need continuous capacity building (31)
Diagnostics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Preference for RDTs (over microscopy) but they are not always available(31) Low sensitivity of RDTs(35) 	
Case investigation		
Complexity of procedures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of standard operating procedures (SOPs)(31) 	
Diagnostics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Old microscopes, limited microscopy experience(31) Insufficient RDTs during high malaria season(48) 	
Data completeness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Difficulty classifying imported v. indigenous cases due to incomplete travel histories(31) 	
Human resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> During high season, a lower proportion of cases were followed up because CHWs were overwhelmed.(48) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> During peak transmission times, the programme would benefit from additional CHWs or suspension of RACD.(4)
Reactive case detection		
Difficult to reach community and terrain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Timely follow up difficult in mountainous terrain or border areas with highly mobile populations (32) Inaccessibility due to flooding(27) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide CHWs with rain gear and boats(27)
Data completeness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Incomplete case investigation forms limits follow-up(34) 	

⁴ Suggestions are those provided in the articles reviewed

	Barriers/Challenges	Solutions⁴
Cross-border issues (national and international)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RACD area extends beyond international border (49) • Most cases are imported from outside the district, district-level response activities alone are likely to be ineffective in interrupting transmission(28) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthened cross-border collaborations needed to ensure adequate coverage of migrant and mobile populations(28) • Communication and surveillance linkages with other operational district malaria response teams are necessary (28)
Diagnostics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RDTs only detect Pf and miss other species and low-density infections(34, 35) • Challenging to ensure a high quality of slides prepared by health centre staff (50) • RDT stockouts prevented testing around index cases(23) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consider LAMP/more sensitive diagnostics(31)
Human Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of health facility workers to conduct malaria activities(36) • At district level, lack of surveillance officers, resulting in inadequate supervision, case investigation and follow-up (34) • Declining motivation among health workers to pursue case investigation and contact testing, particularly during weekends and public holidays (27, 28) • Large numbers of households to screen (51) due to high density of people in small areas(33) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintaining workforce motivation and need for consistent support, supervision and incentives(27)

¹ Suggestions are those provided in the articles reviewed

Table 9 Proportion of household reached by RACD

Country/Region	Proportion of households reached⁵	Proportion of households reached in a timely manner⁶
China (Jiangsu)(36)	19/19 (100%)	19/19 (100%)
Indonesia (Ache)(36)	57/58 (98%)	47/58 (81)
Thailand (Ranong)(36)	271/419 (65%)	229/271 (85%)
Ethiopia (Amhara)(52)	220/407 (54%) index cases identified, were investigated	N/A
Zambia(52) (Kalomo, Choma and Namwala Districts)	62%	N/A
Zanzibar(47)	49% of index case households	about 20% (inferred from Fig2)

⁵ Numerator is the number of RACD events required based on local stratification criteria determining receptive areas.

⁶ For China, Indonesia, and Thailand, target timeliness was within 7 days.

Table 10 Cost per person screened during RACD

Country	General costs (without diagnostics)	Additional diagnostic costs			
		RDT	PCR	Microscopy	LAMP
Indonesia(37)	\$11.00	Not reported	Not reported	\$0.62	\$16.00
Senegal(53)	\$13.94	\$0.36	Not reported	Not reported	Not reported
Thailand(54)	\$3.96	Not reported	\$1.25	Not reported	Not reported

Table 11 RACD cost components from and Indonesia and Senegal

Cost components	Indonesia (Aceh Province)(37)	Senegal (Richard Toll district)(38)
% personnel	41%	37%
% training	20%	29%
% capital (e.g., tablets, lab, vehicles, etc.)	13%	10%
% consumables (e.g., lab supplies, reagents, treatment)	9%	3%
% other (utilities, internet, communication, vehicle rental/fuel)	17%	N/A

Table 12 Number and composition of RACD screening team

	Indonesia(55)	Zambia- Urban(46)	Zambia- Rural(46)
Team Number	5 people	4 people	1 person
Team Composition	Microscopist, 2 CHW's, surveillance officer, and study field coordinator	Environmental health technician, nurse, 2 CHW's	CHW
Follow-up	Up to 2 return visits conducted	1 CHW to follow up 1 index case (over 1 day)	1 CHW to follow up 1 index case (over 1 day)

References:

1. WHO handbook for guideline development. 2014.
2. Booth, A., et al., *Taking account of context in systematic reviews and guidelines considering a complexity perspective*. *BMJ Glob Health*, 2019. **4**(Suppl 1): p. e000840.
3. Bekolo, C.E. and T.D. Williams, *Adding proactive and reactive case detection into the integrated community case management system to optimise diagnosis and treatment of malaria in a high transmission setting of Cameroon: an observational quality improvement study*. *BMJ Open*, 2019. **9**(6): p. e026678.
4. Roberts, K.W., et al., *Community acceptance of reactive focal mass drug administration and reactive focal vector control using indoor residual spraying, a mixed-methods study in Zambezi region, Namibia*. *Malar J*, 2021. **20**(1): p. 162.
5. Littrell, M., et al., *Case investigation and reactive case detection for malaria elimination in northern Senegal*. *Malaria Journal*, 2013. **12**: p. 331.
6. Lohfeld, L., et al., *A qualitative review of implementer perceptions of the national community-level malaria surveillance system in Southern Province, Zambia*. *Malaria Journal*, 2016. **15**(1): p. 400.
7. Kheang, S.T., et al., *Malaria elimination using the 1-3-7 approach: lessons from Sampov Loun, Cambodia*. *BMC Public Health*, 2020. **20**(1): p. 544.
8. Hustedt, J., et al., *Reactive case-detection of malaria in Pailin Province, Western Cambodia: lessons from a year-long evaluation in a pre-elimination setting*. *Malar J*, 2016. **15**: p. 132.
9. van der Horst, T., et al., *Operational Coverage and Timeliness of Reactive Case Detection for Malaria Elimination in Zanzibar, Tanzania*. *Am J Trop Med Hyg*, 2020. **102**(2): p. 298-306.
10. Lu, G., et al., *Challenges in and lessons learned during the implementation of the 1-3-7 malaria surveillance and response strategy in China: a qualitative study*. *Infect Dis Poverty*, 2016. **5**(1): p. 94.
11. Lu, G., et al., *Challenges of foci investigation in malaria elimination program in China: A qualitative study*. *European Journal of Epidemiology*, 2016. **31** (Supplement 1): p. S121-S122.
12. Wang, D., et al., *Adapting the local response for malaria elimination through evaluation of the 1-3-7 system performance in the China-Myanmar border region*. *Malaria Journal*, 2017. **16**(1): p. 54.
13. van Eijk, A.M., et al., *What is the value of reactive case detection in malaria control? A case-study in India and a systematic review*. *Malaria Journal*, 2016. **15**: p. 67.
14. Chihanga, S., et al., *Malaria elimination in Botswana, 2012-2014: achievements and challenges*. *Parasit Vectors*, 2016. **9**: p. 99.
15. Cotter, C., et al., *Piloting a programme tool to evaluate malaria case investigation and reactive case detection activities: results from 3 settings in the Asia Pacific*. *Malaria Journal*, 2017. **16**(1): p. 347.
16. Wangdi, K., et al., *Development and evaluation of a spatial decision support system for malaria elimination in Bhutan*. *Malaria Journal*, 2016. **15**: p. 180.
17. Hsiang, M.S., et al., *Active Case Finding for Malaria: A 3-Year National Evaluation of Optimal Approaches to Detect Infections and Hotspots Through Reactive Case Detection in the Low-transmission Setting of Eswatini*. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*, 2020. **70**(7): p. 1316-1325.
18. Stuck, L., et al., *Malaria infection prevalence and sensitivity of reactive case detection in Zanzibar*. *International Journal of Infectious Diseases*, 2020. **97**: p. 337-346.

19. Zelman, B.W., et al., *Costs and cost-effectiveness of malaria reactive case detection using loop-mediated isothermal amplification compared to microscopy in the low transmission setting of Aceh Province, Indonesia*. *Malaria Journal*, 2018. **17**(1): p. 220.
20. Conner, R.O., et al., *Correction to: Mass testing and treatment for malaria followed by weekly fever screening, testing and treatment in Northern Senegal: feasibility, cost and impact*. *Malar J*, 2020. **19**(1): p. 443.
21. Galactionova, K., et al., *Costing malaria interventions from pilots to elimination programmes*. *Malaria Journal*, 2020. **19**(1): p. 332.
22. Larson, B.A., et al., *A framework for evaluating the costs of malaria elimination interventions: an application to reactive case detection in Southern Province of Zambia, 2014*. *Malaria Journal*, 2016. **15**(1): p. 408.
23. Herdiana, H., et al., *Malaria risk factor assessment using active and passive surveillance data from Aceh Besar, Indonesia, a low endemic, malaria elimination setting with Plasmodium knowlesi, Plasmodium vivax, and Plasmodium falciparum*. *Malaria Journal*, 2016. **15**: p. 468.
24. Larsen, D.A., et al., *Malaria surveillance in low-transmission areas of Zambia using reactive case detection*. *Malaria Journal*, 2015. **14**: p. 465.
25. Van Der Horst, T., et al., *Operational coverage and timeliness of reactive case detection for malaria elimination in Zanzibar, Tanzania*. *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*, 2020. **102**(2): p. 298-306.
26. Searle, K.M., et al., *Evaluation of the operational challenges in implementing reactive screen-and-treat and implications of reactive case detection strategies for malaria elimination in a region of low transmission in southern Zambia*. *Malaria Journal*, 2016. **15**(1): p. 412.
27. Wangdi, K., et al., *Development and evaluation of a spatial decision support system for malaria elimination in Bhutan*. *Malar J*, 2016. **15**: p. 180.
28. Hustedt, J., et al., *Reactive case-detection of malaria in Pailin Province, Western Cambodia: lessons from a year-long evaluation in a pre-elimination setting*. *Malaria Journal*, 2016. **15**: p. 132.
29. Smith Gueye, C., et al., *Active case detection for malaria elimination: a survey among Asia Pacific countries*. *Malaria Journal*, 2013. **12**(1): p. 358.
30. Bansil, P., et al., *Malaria case investigation with reactive focal testing and treatment: operational feasibility and lessons learned from low and moderate transmission areas in Amhara Region, Ethiopia*. *Malaria Journal*, 2018. **17**(1): p. 449.
31. Conner, R.O., et al., *Mass testing and treatment for malaria followed by weekly fever screening, testing and treatment in Northern Senegal: feasibility, cost and impact*. *Malar J*, 2020. **19**(1): p. 252.
32. Rogawski, E.T., et al., *Active case detection with pooled real-time PCR to eliminate malaria in Trat province, Thailand*. *Am J Trop Med Hyg*, 2012. **86**(5): p. 789-91.
33. Herdiana, H., et al., *Use of active and passive surveillance to determine the risk factors for malaria infection in aceh besar, indonesia, a low-endemic, multi-species setting (plasmodium knowlesi, P. vivax, and P. falciparum infection) aiming for malaria elimination*. *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*, 2016. **95** (5 Supplement 1): p. 280.